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**THE CHANGING NATURE OF COMMUNITY MEDIA: A CASE STUDY OF
DIGITAL SHIFT AMONG SELECTED PUBLICATIONS IN THE
PROVINCE OF CAVITE, PHILIPPINES**

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22 May 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **REGEL LINCUNA MOZOL** with the title: “**THE CHANGING NATURE OF COMMUNITY MEDIA: A CASE STUDY OF DIGITAL SHIFT AMONG SELECTED PUBLICATIONS IN THE PROVINCE OF CAVITE, PHILIPPINES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Development Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

“Kagaya ng bulaklak na mirasól, dumating man ang ilang ulan o mainitan sa paghihintay, masisilayan pa rin ang pamumukadkad sa pagsapit ng buwang liwayway.”

Born on the 21st of June 1995, Regel L. Mozol is the second child of Ms. Raquel and Mr. Estanislao Mozol Jr. He started writing at the young age of four and became passionate in books and drawing materials even before he went to school. He was chosen as the editorial cartoonist in their elementary paper and continued his craft in high school as he joined several writing contests and poster making events. Aside from these, he is also a Tae Kwon Do practitioner and competed in different tournaments inside and outside the province of Cavite.

At present, he and his family are residing in the City of Imus. He is also working at Cavite State University Main Campus as one of the faculty members of the Department of Communication where he teaches Photojournalism, Multimedia, Documentary Filmmaking, and Community Journalism course.

Aside from being a communication and journalism educator, Regel was trained as a Korean as a Foreign Language (KFL) Teacher in the Philippines supervised by UP Department of Linguistics and Korea Research Center.

Due to his undergraduate exposure in community media and his desire to bring hope to the voiceless, he pursued his Master of Development Communication degree at the University of the Philippines Open University and successfully earned it in December 2024.

In his free time, he prefers to stay alone; he is either watching films under his blanket or reading endless books buried on his little shelf.

Acknowledgement

As a small-town researcher who juggles multiple jobs, I experienced obstacles and setbacks that tried to prevent me from finishing my thesis. I would have never accomplished this if it was not because of these people who supported me and generously shared colors during some of the greyest days in my life.

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God, You kept your promise that you will go before me and you would never leave me nor forsake me. Your grace made it happen. All glory and praise belong to You, Lord.

And lastly, thank you for holding on, self. I know you wanted to give up after all the tragedies you went through but you continued to find courage and reasons to move forward. This story of *Sablay* will remain immortal. Please know that you are not a sad story, you are alive, and there are more spaces where you have every right to choose the shade of color you want in painting your new chapters. Your *puhon* is now here.

Dedication

For *Mama Raquel* who first believed in me that I could finish my master's degree, thank you. When I was a small child and merely trying to express different colors of myself, you shielded and supported me from the hatred of the outside world. You generously sprinkled your pixie dust to ensure my own wings can overcome gravity. You taught me love even before I knew what love is. You always compromise your morning to get me a *baon* or lunch in school and even at work, and that love gave me more motivation to keep going. Ma, your Toto is now a UP graduate!

For *Mary Pearl*, my lovely Libra sister, your art piece and your sweet little gifts made from gentle love and care, you are also my inspiration. I dedicate this success to you and mama.

As for those who doubted themselves and felt insignificant, let me remind you, just like the main point of my thesis, you have every right to claim your place in this world and you will always be relevant. You are important.

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Abstract

Using a case study approach, this master thesis conducted in-depth interviews with the heads or editors-in-chief of five (5) publications in the province of Cavite. With ethical considerations in mind, the interview yielded meaningful narratives that shed light on how community media continues to adapt in a digital environment. The researcher used an interview guide, a coding sheet, and thematic analysis to explore the "then" and "now" of the selected papers, which underwent a digitization process. Essentially, themes surfaced and were employed to elucidate how community media is adjusting in terms of ownership, manpower, financial resources, production process, and distribution.

In accordance with the analysis, the research revealed that the ownership has not changed since then as most of the publications are still reliant on government support while the other one thrives as a private-owned newspaper. In terms of adaptability, a lot of them were forced to decrease their manpower since in their case, they needed to decrease their size. Others, however, found it to be a struggle since some of them had to shoulder the responsibility of content creation all by themselves.

Additionally, the study clarified how these publications' production altered as a result of reduced delays brought on by time flexibility and the introduction of technology, which made it easier for them to obtain their sources and presented a chance for innovation. Furthermore, their packaging is still ethically upright despite modifications, particularly when it comes to using human sources. They are

making an extra effort to be social media responsible because they are now navigating online. Maintaining the paper digitally requires a certain level of familiarity to maintain not only the effective dissemination of information but also the development of integrity and harmony with their community.

As a result, community media continues to stand firm and, despite maintaining its distinctive nature in the digital age, the stories drawn from each case demonstrated that these local newspapers continue to adhere to the ideals and standards of civic journalism. Therefore, these local newspapers and newsletters are co-existing to raise awareness on issues concerned and highlight realities in the hopes of seeing people fulfill their potential to advance as individuals and eventually create an informed society.

Keywords: Community Journalism; Community Media; Development Journalism; Digital Shift

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Over the years, community media has been recognized as crucial and has demonstrated its critical role in social mobilization in remote places. Community media continues to exist and fulfill its function as technology works to improve and advance areas that require assistance with the dissemination of news and information. As cited in the book *Philippine Communication in the Digital Age* by Dr. Crispin Maslog (2014), community media was classified as a new trend in the use of communication media for community development. Dr. Maslog added that while mass media are more efficient in mass dissemination of information, they are not as effective in getting people involved in problems and issues of their communities. Hence, small media provides better access and opportunities for people participation in community development (Maslog, 2014).

One of the highlighted roles of a news outlet within the community, according to a study "Toward a Measure of Community Journalism" (Mass Communication & Society, 2008), is the ability to effectively deliver information from community leaders, officials, experts, and organizations that is useful and pertinent to community members. In a nutshell, this is the importance of development journalism as well, since it is referred to as "statist," and is seen as a willing collaborator of the government in development projects and a substitute media for community objectives and directions.

In the framework of this study, municipalities in Cavite were using newsletters and a newspaper even prior to the pandemic to document occurrences and share information with their residents. In order to deliver news in a newsletter, information must be gathered and organized and at the same time articles must also be brief yet accurate. Accordingly, to evaluate news for public efficiency of a community newsletter, publicist Norman Wiley (2014) considered readership relevance, meaningfulness, discovery, impact/scale, time scale, development, controversy, source, angle, and human interest. As a result, it requires focusing on human interest and communicating on what is new or different within the community.

Furthermore, the majority of the newsletters used as references in this study were originally given out in person or could be taken inside the workplace. However, newsletters were impacted by physical limitations imposed by safety precautions designed to battle the COVID-19 virus, leading to the creation of pandemic-driven content or electronic newsletters. According to a *2022 CSM Tech* article, digital shift or transformation is the process of rethinking how a business uses disruptive innovations to advance, hence changing its culture. It occurs when an organization adopts new procedures and instruments that enhance performance.

The researcher analyzed and clarified how Cavite's community media evolved and how traditional news sources have given way to their electronic or digital equivalents in this case study. In particular, it aimed to clarify how a conventional medium changed in the digital era and how such changes impacted the environment. Following the collection of qualitative data, certain

factors were found, and themes were analyzed. Although the scope in terms of geographical location is small, the outcome explored the situation of community media before and amid pandemic and would provide more understanding of dimensions in the occurrence of digital shift among printed newsletters.

Statement of the Problem

This study digested and critically explained how community media in Cavite is transforming within the digital environment.

The following specific problems were highlighted to answer the aforementioned general problem:

1. How community media in Cavite is changing in this digital environment in terms of:
 - a. Media Ownership
 - b. Budget Allocation
 - c. Manpower?
2. How the production process in selected community media is changing in this digital environment in terms of:
 - a. Content Gathering
 - b. Content Packaging?
3. How the distribution process in selected community media is changing in this digital environment in terms of:
 - a. Medium or Outlet
 - b. Frequency of Releasing?

Objectives of the Study

Generally, the research studied the changing nature of community media in the province of Cavite particularly its transformation in a digital environment.

Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Explain the changing nature of selected community media in a digital environment in terms of:
 - a. Media Ownership
 - b. Budget Allocation
 - c. Manpower
2. Analyze the changing nature of production process in selected community media in terms of:
 - a. Content Gathering
 - b. Content Packaging
3. Explain the changing nature of distribution process in selected community media in terms of:
 - a. Medium or Outlet
 - b. Frequency of Releasing

Significance of the Study

One perceived role of the changing nature of community media is its ability to adapt to the needs and demands of the people. Aside from the arrival of technological advancement, community media served its purpose when COVID-19 virus brought disruption among countries that affected even the

smallest groups. These are just some among multiple reasons as to why this study is beneficial.

The **editorial staff and local officers of municipalities among provinces** who also experienced a digital shift would be enlightened more and potentially find solace through the narratives of the informants in this study. Thus, it may provide more understanding on their resilience and capabilities to produce and disseminate information in the midst of technological challenges.

The development journalism perspective in this study might add new knowledge towards **community development** through pandemic-driven newsletters or the electronic ones as these materials can be studied and analyzed as proliferators of mobilization. As mentioned in a study, a community newspaper or newsletter is one that helps readers understand their environment. It also helps its readers change that environment by crusading when that seems wise. Lastly, a community newspaper is supposed to create a community spirit.

This study, once presented to the **local government offices**, has a high chance of securing financial support since it can enlighten the stakeholders of the difficulty of producing contents online as it requires equipment and internet connectivity. Likewise, they could understand how traditional and electronic materials such as IEC materials and the like must be looked at as an effective tool or change agents in keeping their development goals and initiatives transparent in the community radar.

Finally, because it helps deepen their grasp of the influence of community media, this study is also helpful to **scholars studying development communication**. This study can serve as a reference for future

research with focus on the case of those who struggled to maintain newspapers and newsletters in the digital shift.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The researcher focused on studying the changing nature of community media in selected municipalities in Cavite. It was made possible through the involvement of each head or the editor-in-chief in an in-depth interview.

Moreover, the researcher visited selected municipalities in Cavite that have an existing newsletter or newspaper. The head or the editor-in-charge of the paper was the main target of the researcher. Other information like their professional identity or educational background was not included as it can be a sensitive subject for them.

Operational Definition of Terminologies

Community Media – It refers to the smaller tools used in news and information dissemination among small groups or communities. Specifically, the medium that the researcher focused on in this study is newsletter or newspaper managed by the local government unit (LGU) and it served as one of the vital keys to understand the phenomenon regarding the changing nature of community media.

Content Gathering – It is included in the interview guide question to gather information as to how the staffs of the newsletter select and collect news and information for their content in the digital environment.

Content Packaging – It was analyzed to understand how these newsletters produce their copies then and now. It includes lay-outing, style sheet, graphics presentation, etcetera.

Development Journalism – As a graduate student of development communication, the researcher based the unit of analysis on the perspective of development journalism as it provides contribution to better understand the importance of community media.

Digital Shift – It happens when a traditional medium converges to or adopts new technology. In this study, the researcher analyzed how traditional, or the printed newsletters underwent digital shift and the challenges that this phenomenon gives among the staff of the publication.

Frequency of Releasing – This was included in the interview guide question to gather information as to how many times the newsletter releases a copy or issue.

Pandemic-driven Newsletter – In this study, the researcher used this term to pertain to those newsletters who created an online counterpart to continue their publication in the midst of disruption brought by COVID-19 virus.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents related literature and studies used by the researcher in this study.

Communication for Development

Interpersonal communication, classical methods, multimedia: the concept of C4D subsumes a wide range of very different tools, methods and channels.

Dialogue is the most appropriate word to summarize the concept of communication for development. In this respect it is very different from institutional communication, which delivers one-way information to a dispersed target audience with often indistinct features. In contrast, communication for development strives to establish an exchange with people on an equal footing. It targets specific groups of people in a clearly defined social and cultural environment in order to identify their concerns and needs and foster their participation.

C4D can also enhance the visibility of a development agent, but this is not its primary goal. C4D always aims to promote development in order to contribute to social change. Communication tools are a means, not an end. It is the quality of the process – rather than a specific output – which makes all the difference; and the aim of the process is to promote social participation, strengthen the sense of ownership of a project and hence its impact. Human

development takes time. Where it does take place, it is not only the result of technical improvements but also of lengthy and intensive social and communication processes.

Moreover, C4D is not a specific communication discipline, but rather acts as a hinge between communication and project management. C4D leverages the social and political impact of a project. This is why it requires close cooperation and an effective division of tasks between technical experts and communication specialists. The former identifies the messages and topics for debate, while the latter determine the tools for dissemination and spaces for dialogue.

Community Media

According to Ramirez (1989), the community press or media in particular is still too often thought of as the “local rag”. The reasons for the supreme importance of its being at the local government as an alternative means of expression between the people of a locality and the country as a whole have been given.

He added that the community media, more than any other institution, can give that first feeling of “belonging” to a new community so necessary for any sort of balanced behavior. Through its editorial columns, its articles, even its advertisements, a community sense can be developed more quickly and more easily than by any other medium. The community media as a whole, adapts itself to the changing social patterns and to inform the people of all events in the area (Ramirez, 1989).

In history, community journalism or community press got its name from a Montana editor, Ken Byerly, while he was a professor of journalism at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Although the term is relatively new, community journalism has been around since the founding fathers. He gave it its name because the concept had been referred to as "Hometown Newspapers," which did not fit the suburban newspapers at that time (Lauterer, 1995).

In addition, community media is locally oriented, professional news coverage that typically focuses on city neighborhoods, individual suburbs or small towns, rather than metropolitan, state, national or world news. Community journalism concentrates on the effect they have on local readers. Thus, community newspapers or newsletters, often but not always publish weekly, and also tend to cover subjects larger news media do not. Some examples of topics are students on the honor roll at the local high school, school sports, crimes such as vandalism, zoning issues and other details of community life. However, such "hyperlocal" articles are sometimes dismissed as "chicken dinner" stories (Lauterer, 1995).

Furthermore, through a qualitative and quantitative content analysis of scholarship on community and news media, community news media according to Lowrey (2008) should:

- (a) Facilitate the process of negotiating and making meaning about community
- (b) Reveal or ensure understanding of community structure

In accordance, numerous studies in this analysis suggest that any scale measure of community journalism should accommodate the impact of the community's power structure on news decisions and should address the need for inclusion of less powerful voices.

According to an article "*Community blogging: The new wave of citizen journalism*," community journalism would ideally reveal, or make individuals aware of, spaces, institutions, resources, events, and ideas that may be shared, and encourage such sharing. The practice should also facilitate the process of negotiating and making meaning about a community.

Community Newspaper/ Newsletter

Community newspapers according to Black and Thompson (1998) are generally small, daily operations serving the provincial interests of isolated communities or discrete suburbs.

According to them, these community newspapers meet two specific needs: they provide suburban dwellers with information about their communities, and they offer local merchants a vehicle through which to advertise their products and sales. They furthered that community newspapers provide local merchants and advertising showcase for the communities they serve at prices proportionate to exposure.

However, under the most trying conditions which are a far-cry to the affluent metropolitan setting, the struggling community press somehow manages to perform its avowed mission in forging ahead new frontiers of progress and change through the dissemination of information.

Delivering of news in a community newspaper/ newsletter involves collecting information and organization that also counts on making the article/s short but precise. It requires focusing on human interest and communicating on what is new or different within the community in which Norman, Publicist, Wiley (2014) considered the relevance of readership, meaningfulness, discovery, impact/ scale, time scale, development, controversy, source, angle, and human interest as ways of evaluating news for public efficiency of a community newsletter.

According to Freedman (2011), having an effective news report is often dictated by the many thoughtful choices made by editors and journalists. Newsletters let the audience harness and understand the power of the audience and use their feedback to develop more news reports. It also deepens the understanding of audience reaction and how to handle the feedback.

Criteria for Community Media or Community Journalism

In a study "*Toward a Measure of Community Journalism*" (Mass Communication & Society, 2008), one way to measure the degree to which news outlets reveal community structure is the following list:

- Communities with contact information for community leaders, officials, experts, and community organizations.
- Information from community leaders, officials, experts, and community organizations that are usable and relevant to community members.
- Information on community services and institutions.
- Information so that communities understand how to use services and institutions.

- Information on clubs and organizations.
- Information that helps communities understand how to get involved with local or relevant clubs and organizations.
- Information that helps communities take advantage of local or relevant events and festivities.

Current Situation of Community Newspapers/ Newsletters in the Philippines

The community newspaper today enjoys a tremendous amount of prestige and influence as a result of the generally judicious way in which it has exercised its freedom (Roces, 1969). He added that the influence is seen particularly in the way government officials in the countryside constantly seek its support for their programs and, conversely, fear any criticism from the press, which often does a better job of fiscalizing the provincial and municipal administration than the opposition party.

In accordance, Roces (1969), former publisher of the old *Manila Times* pointed that the central issue of community newspapers in the Philippines today is to develop in such a way that they can be financially stable, editorially competent, unrestrained in expression, responsive to the needs of readers and responsible to the community. Part of the things that he mentioned also is the idea that they will be newspapers that will owe allegiance not to political leaders, specific administrators or even cultural groups. Hence, their loyalty must be subjected to values, to ideals, and to human beings.

Another explanation of community newspapers was defined by Maslog (1993) and according to him, these are “small business enterprises” which are

“making small profit at best, breaking even most of the time, or losing money at worst.” These definitions contain two general concepts about community newspapers: business enterprise and profit. Community newspapers, sometimes called local newspapers, are usually family-owned. Being relatively small, these local papers have the tendency to be “financially stable” (Maslog, 1993). Initially, funding comes from the owners, with little expectation from the profit since most local papers do not cost that much.

However, regardless of the different challenges faced by community newspapers, there is an increase in the numbers of local papers in some provinces in the Philippines. In a recent study of Soriano and Vargas (2013), they researched the growth and increase in the number of community newspapers in Pangasinan. According to them, the positive change in the number of community newspapers in the said province is mainly because the industry there is not dead at all. There are still clients who advertise on the newspaper to help them survive (Soriano & Vargas, 2013). Also, they added that the contents of these newspapers are also contributing to the said growth. Some newspapers in the province feature the culture of the place which in turn will attract tourists.

The continuous publication of community newspapers as well as their proliferation in some provinces in the country, suggest that the industry is not dead, contrary to the notion that the modernization of the media like digitization will kill the print medium. Perhaps the purpose of the community newspapers makes them strong and alive (Soriano & Vergara, 2013).

Community newspapers' readers play a vital role in its continuous publication. Their perceptions and receptions to a local paper will determine if they patronize it or not. In the book of Janowitz (1967), part of his research was the study of imagery or the reader's reactions to the newspaper's general format and content character. He discovered through the reader's responses four themes that encompass the image of community newspapers: First, the readers perceive these sets of newspapers as "auxiliary" and not as competitors of daily press. It is also noted that as compared to the daily press, community press has the tendency to be viewed more favourably due to the kind of reporting it does which covers those that happen in the immediate community (p. 143). Second, they view the community press as a non-commercial medium. Third, this press is viewed as an "agent of community welfare and progress" and not necessarily partisan, further noting that politics can be a threat to the overall appeal of the paper (p. 147-148). Lastly, it is also viewed as an "extension of the reader's personal and social contacts because of its emphasis on news about local voluntary associations and local social and personal news" (p. 149). Such themes related how the readers perceived the community press. Once these themes are violated, it can affect the readership significantly.

Gallardo (2008) claimed that community newspapers not only provide just news and "relevant" information to the people, they also "bring change for the good." For instance, in Cagayan de Oro, which has a corrupt environment, community newspapers do something to bring about change and publish news which is generally peaceful and does not push for violence, basically because it is what the community needs.

Some community newspapers also have agendas which for its owners and editors are necessary because these will play a vital role in survival. Pampanga Times, one of the oldest community papers in Pampanga, usually publish articles which are generally positive because it wants to promote the business for locality (Paldeng, 1993). That news which can turn investors off will be avoided to preserve the alive business industry in the province (Paldeng, 1993). Weekly Ilocos Times, the first newspaper in La Union, also does the same. It publishes news in accordance with its thrust which is about business, as well as development journalism (Rubio, 1993).

Development Journalism

It is the result of development journalism that today the public at large is aware of various ill-effects of deforestation such as pollution, water related problems, sand erosion, etc. Development journalism has forced the public to re-think about development goals and strategies. Many media writers have used the issue of development and the means to achieve developmental goals to write a number of very intriguing reports. Reports of development journalists should be structured around following facts and data:

- I. A development reporter should collect data from that specific area which has already been developed. For this, it is essential to interview the people involved in coordinating various development works in that area or were associated with them in one way or another and it is also important to take the points of view of the officials involved in the execution; inspection or any other activity directly related to different developmental activities going on in that area.

II. It is important to be factual while writing development-based news reports.

III. It is more important for a development reporter to have her/his own perspectives regarding any specific developmental activity or plan than to have a distinctive style or technique of writing.

IV. Language of development reporters should be as simple and easy as possible. While giving statistics related to development such as income, expenditure, literacy rate, etc., it is preferable to give whole numbers instead of fractions.

V. Comparative numbers or statistics are always helpful. For example, if one is writing a report about the effects of new technology on the existing communication system, then the report can be made more effective by incorporating a comparative analysis of the current situation with the situation that existed before the aforementioned technology was deployed. By putting comparative data side by side, a clear picture can be presented to the reader or the audience.

Editorial Board

Based on report from the *Trade Association Business Publications International* (2024), the editorial board operates as the voice of the paper and the publisher. It is composed of experts in different news beats as politics, economics, state and local affairs, education, criminal justice, health and science, international affairs, and more. The editor-in-chief, also referred to as the executive editor, is a member of the editorial board and is primarily in charge of the newspaper's editorial direction and content acquisition. He or she

develops the editorial direction and tone of each magazine based on the editorial director's vision. The chief editor bears the responsibility of guaranteeing that each edition aligns with the publication's goals and principles.

Bennet (202), however, argued that the editorial board does not always represent the organization. Journalists are people with differing perspectives, but it is their responsibility to put such differences aside in the quest and presenting of the truth.

Importance of Communication in Rural Areas

Communication is a multi-faceted aspect of community life. It can act as a glue to bind people together, as oil to lubricate social and economic relations, and as a web to mark lines of influence and interaction. Communication is important for the transmission and interaction among community members, as well as for its role in creating society and culture. As John Dewey stated, "Society not only continues to exist by transmission, by communication, but it may fairly be said to exist in transmission, in communication...men [sic] live in a community in virtue of the things they have in common; and communication is the way in which they come to possess things in common."

The existence of commonality among members of a community can have an important impact on achieving shared goals and [something about rural areas]. It is evident that communication is an inherent part of rural capacity building. This should come as no surprise, for, as noted above, communication could be said to Westcott (2002) particularly stresses the importance of grass

roots communication (“bottom up”) to the capacity development process. This is echoed by Rothenbuhler (2001), who suggests that capacity building must come from within a community, rather than through the outside intervention of “experts,” and that this can only happen through discourse between and among community members. Equally important is the role that communication plays in fostering social cohesion and social capital. Ken’idi (2002), for example, notes that it is the day-to-day interactions that form the bulk of our social networks, so the role of communication is vital to social capital development: “Our daily communication takes place in interpersonal informal situations, more often than in intermediate organizations. Thus, the focus is on the role of daily interpersonal situations as basis upon which society in all its facets is built. Capacity building can be defined as activities that increase an individual’s, a population’s or a community’s ability for growth, development, or accomplishment. In much of the literature, it is defined much more specifically as “Activities, resources and support that strengthen the skills and abilities of people and community groups to take effective action and leading roles in the development of their communities” (Community Safety Advisory Service, www.csa.gov.za/, n.d.).

The ease and efficiency with which information can be circulated using the internet has increased the importance of email and web pages as modes of communication. However, in communities which have little or no access to internet services, Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs) become somewhat irrelevant; the digital divide does not exist just between rich and poor nations, but is firmly entrenched within even the richest countries. The literature suggests clearly that simply adding ICTs to the mix of community

development will not necessarily create a strong and vibrant community. Preece (2002), although exploring the role that ICTs may have for social cohesion in a post-9/11 world, stresses that off-line communication is equally important in creating strong communities. Emke (2001; 2003) has conducted extensive research into the role of community newspapers in creating community identity in rural Canada (see also Emke, Bruce, and Wilkinson, forthcoming).

Media Ecology Theory

Media Ecology, led by Marshall McLuhan, is the study of different personal and social environments created by the use of different communication technologies. McLuhan claimed that changes to technology alter the human symbolic environment. Just as the age of literacy began to separate individuals, McLuhan saw the electronic age as re-tribalizing the human race. However, instead of small, isolated villages of the tribal age, people began to move towards becoming a connected, global village.

Moreover, Neil Postman famously used a biological metaphor to explain “media ecology,” a term he borrowed from McLuhan to spearhead an intellectual tradition. In biology, a medium is defined as a substance within which a culture grows; in media ecology, a medium is a technology within which human culture grows, giving form to its politics, ideologies, and social organization.

Previously, “medium” had been conceptualized in terms of transportation; now in communication studies it is typically understood as an environment. Media ecology focuses on media as environments, and

environments as media, with an explicit concern for their evolution, effects, and forms. It comprises a theory about the complex interplay between humans, technology, media, and the environment, with the aim of increasing awareness of mutual effects.

Media ecology is an expansive, inclusive, and therefore multidisciplinary field, borrowing from a range of academic disciplines, including technology and information studies, linguistics and semiotics, and cultural studies.

“Media” refers to communication technologies as well as other communicative forms, such as the brain and body, the classroom and the courtroom, and the languages, symbols, and codes of successive historical eras.

“Ecology” is also a transgressive and encompassing term, drawing upon systems theory and cybernetics in order to make sense of the evolution of humans and technology in the coproduction of culture. Media ecology is distinct from communication studies proper in its focus on the integration, interdependence, and dynamism of media and technology in human affairs. It assumes that the symbol systems and technologies people use to think with, communicate, and represent experiences play an integral role in how human creates and understand reality. As symbols and media have evolved significantly since the invention of the alphabet—hailed as the first communication technology—so have the thinking processes, social and political structures, and conceptions of reality.

Media ecology provides a lens for understanding these changes as people experience and represent “the world” through the ever-new media and symbols. Media ecology thus explores the cultural consequences of how media

change—and change humans—over time. One lingering criticism of the approach is that of technological determinism, not least because of the early thinkers' preoccupation with the causal role of media in societal change. Media ecologists have responded by underscoring their focus on the interaction of communication, culture, and consciousness as a dynamic process rather than on communication technology as the singular and driving force of social transformation.

People Behind Community Media

Since community media only serves a specific community, the manpower of community newspapers is generally smaller as compared to the national newspapers. Since there is a problem financially, media organizations in the community just hire journalists who will be assigned or just take a certain task. “It is not surprising to encounter a community-based print publication that has only one or two people who do all the work” (Arao, 2010).

The problem with the high cost of the production process, specifically printing, is seen as a main hindrance in hiring full-time reporters. The owners of some community newspapers rely mainly on press releases or free updates from local government agencies which makes their content “written in the same perspective” (Soriano & Vargas, 2013).

Most editorial staff of community newspapers also **lack training and experience** prior to entering the publications (Maslog, 1993). In a study conducted by Yapo and Cabrera (1990) on community journalism in Southern Tagalog, aside from production issues and other external constraints, some community newspapers also problematize inadequacy of editorial staff which

includes “lack of sufficient editorial staff, lack of journalistic skills and experience, and lack of professional education and training.”

But despite this, a good number of editors had their informal training when they served as “correspondent or staff member of other newspapers before joining their present newspapers” or as “campus journalists” (Maslog, 1993). Most of them do not necessarily had degree in journalism but are still hired to work for these community newspapers.

Competition is also a problem for many local newspapers. Some source of competition can be from Manila dailies which many people still opt to read instead of the community newspapers. One reason can be because “an important local newsbreak which could take up a week to be reported in the local paper could be read in a Manila daily the following day” (Ingles & Maceda, 1981).

Problems Faced by Community Editor

The business and financial aspects of the newspaper are the nagging problems of the community editor. The newspaper is a private business venture, and there is a need to “break-even” the investment in the newspaper business. The major problems encountered by the community editor are the low circulation, less advertisements and the exorbitant printing cost. The book *Philippine journalism handbook* also tells that the newspapers in the provinces cannot cope with the salaries and operational costs. They cannot survive and render public service to the remote areas in the countryside due to dearth advertisements and better printing facilities. Advertising is where the money comes from, and this is indeed important in the field of community journalism.

However, in order to solve the problems of the local press, there is a need to improve the quality, format and editorial content of the community newspapers; better printing facilities and sound management of the business. Meanwhile, in that capacity it has the responsibility to keep the people in its community informed about matters of interest and importance to them. Lastly, many local newspapers in the Philippines today are doing from fair to good jobs in this area, but for the most part there is always room for improvement. It is expected that the improvement in quality will continue with the professionalization of the community newspapers.

Problems of the Community Press

Researchers deemed it necessary to determine how these dilemmas affect the operations of the newspaper. Among the many theses about community newspapers, the results seemed to be unanimous in some aspects.

The lack of financial sources is the most common problem these newspapers face. Boongaling, Laosantos, and Santos (2001) which studied the state of community newspapers in Bulacan from 1995 to 2001. Based on the result of their interview with the editors and other staff of several community newspapers in the province, they have concluded that a stable source of income is highly significant. But the local newspapers in Bulacan during that period not only recognized the problem in terms of financing its operation, but also saw the “unwillingness of the people to support the paper financially” (Boongaling, Laosantos, & Santos, 2001). Also, according to the study the

people “fail to properly recognize the vital role of these papers in the development of the community.”

Production constraints are also frequently problematized by local newspapers. High costs of printing and supplies, as well as the lack of printing equipment, are the primary problems often cited. Power interruptions are also a problem especially if it is frequent and results in costly production delays (Ingles & Maceda, 1981).

In the study on community newspapers cited by Maslog (1993), among the 127 respondents who were working for different local newspapers in the country, 52 percent of them said they continue to publish because they were earning relatively “reasonable or a small profit.” The other respondents said they were just “breaking even” while others said they were “losing” (Maslog, 1993). But despite this, these newspapers editors and owners said they continue publishing because some of them were “subsidized, either for political or business reasons.” Those who said they were just breaking even also justified their continuous operation by saying that they do so because of “livelihood and sense of power and influence in community or for public service.” Maslog concluded that as long as these newspapers gain profit, they will continue to publish.

The manpower of community newspapers is generally smaller as compared to the national newspapers, apparently because it only serves a specific community. Since there is a problem financially, media organizations in community just hire journalists who will be assigned or just take a certain

task. “It is not surprising to encounter community-based print publication that has only one or two people who do all the work” (Arao, 2010).

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local paper could be read in a Manila daily the following day” (Ingles & Maceda, 1981).

The Benefits of Community Newspaper/ Newsletter

The operation of a community newspaper may provide the satisfaction which comes from constructive work well done. Apart from a publisher’s influence, he usually is able to play through his columns a real part in maintaining a wholesome community spirit and in promoting civic betterment and general public welfare and has a clearly implied responsibility to do.

Additionally, a community newspaper is one that helps readers understand their environment. It also helps its readers change that environment by crusading when that seems wise. Lastly, a community newspaper is supposed to create a community spirit. This is true in a metropolitan area where community boundaries are not easily identifiable (Mott *et al.*, 1958).

Moreover, effective delivery of news in a community is like communication, it is about more than just exchanging information, it is about understanding the emotion and intentions behind the information. As well as being able to clearly convey a message, the media outlet also needs to listen in a way that gains the full meaning of what is being said and makes the other person feel heard and understood. Effective delivering of news is not just how one conveys a message or information in which it is received by the people, but it is also how one observes and listens to gain the full meaning of what is being said. It is more like a glue that helps deepen the connection of the community in grasping news in an effective way as stated (Smith, *et. al.*, 2020).

Vraga and Tully (2018) further stated that newsletters also need news exposure to political outcomes. News consumption is notoriously difficult to measure, and misreporting news exposure is common where the audience profiles differ using self-reported versus behavioral measures, creating two different pictures of news exposure. More attention is needed to improve news measurement strategies to address misreporting and to improve the accuracy of news audience profiles.

The Community Press and Development

Provincial newspapers have remained small for they do not receive the support of the local presses, like those in the United States, for example, receive. Their readership is too insignificant and advertisers ignore them. As a consequence, the printing facilities have remained poor and their editorial staffs regard their work more as an avocation than as a real vocation (Feliciano, 1968).

However, a majority of respondents in case studies agree that, where it exists, the provincial press has done a “fairly good job in serving the people’s welfare,” especially by serving:

1. as information medium of the local government;
2. by being watchdog or inspector-general of local government officials and their actuations,
3. by acting as a vehicle for social change, and
4. by transmitting local indigenous culture to the local folk from one generation to another.

According to Wilbur Schramm, the provincial press is an agent of social change. The social change helps to to view customs and practices and, in some cases, to different social relationships. Behind such changes in attitudes, beliefs, skills, and social norms the local press plays a vital role in the community. Data indicate that one who reads newspapers is about three and a half times more likely to develop favorable cognitive attitude toward an innovation. This kind of effect Lerner calls “the great multiplier” in development, for the press can spread new knowledge and attitudes immeasurably more quickly and widely than ever before (Schramm, 1964).

Hence, he added that community press can be instrumental in the solution also of numerous national problems. The community print media could make perhaps its largest contribution in the field of social and cultural problems, and also in education. This is accomplished best when there is an interpersonal link in the process—a teacher to work with the pupil, a discussion group to help decide when new techniques and customs a community shall absorb into its life. Also, the combination of mass media and interpersonal instruction –expert instruction from the provincial media and two-way interaction with a teacher—are thus extraordinarily powerful.

The Community Press as Change Agents

Rivera and McMillan (1954) explained that the community or the provincial press must be seen in the context of its rural surroundings. Rivera and Mcmillan’s description of Central Luzon is perhaps representative of the Philippines, a land of marked contrasts: “great haciendas or estates and masses of landless workers; opportunities for crop diversification versus

emphasis on a single crop; fairly fertile land, but low productivity; growing population against unlimited or undiscovered employment opportunities and discontent in an area of possible peace and order.

Schramm (1964) calls communications as the fundamental social process. "Without communication, human groups and societies would not exist (Feliciano, 1967). It would seem that, as the content of the communication media changes, society is likewise bound to change. It was in fact the influence of the mass media that was thought to be a very strong force in changing society. It was said to create public opinion by mere "calculation, high pressure, witchcraft and bombardment." Hence, its influence was so pervasive that it was almost possible to suspect mass communication as "the bedrock of modern society." But modern research has also revealed the limitations of the power of the print media, like the community press, and has delineated a new role. The functions of the mass media Schramm classified are under three headings:

1. Information function which recognizes the capacity of the mass media to focus attention on the goals of development programs;
2. Decision-making function which reflects the potency of the mass media in bringing about social changes; and
3. Teaching function which sees the adaptability of the mass media to varied educational purposes.

According to Schramm, the mass media can also adequately perform the first task, but need the support of interpersonal communicators to hurdle the second and third tasks, communicators allow themselves too often to be

overwhelmed by the wonders that the mass media are expected to bring about without considering their limitations (Feliciano, 1968).

They also added that if the provincial media were taken to be a powerful influence in socio-cultural change, today that view has been modified to influencing people's attitudes towards social change. Thus, the media deal with, not just innovation, but first and primarily with people. The community press is not an instrument of change in and of itself, but a tool affecting many other channels and instruments of change. It must discriminate information, spread knowledge, and thus educate the masses. They explained also that to make people conducive to change, they must first be educated. In fact, the communications of the community papers and the process of education are equivalent: communication is education, and education is communication.

According to an Indian research, the community press helped to promote literature and science through the dissemination of knowledge among the uneducated masses by reading and discussion of essays and literary, historical, and social subjects, by lectures on physical and chemical science accompanied by experiments, and by the publication of cheap monthly periodical literature suited to the requirements and tastes of the people (Parikh, 1951).

According to the book *Problems of Development in Asia*, it is in this context that people must consider the local print media as an agent of change. It can help to change attitudes, to predispose people to change, but it cannot overwhelm the public with a barrage of information and achieve an end by that

alone. The book also explained that hand in hand with education, it can be a powerful tool in the implementation of social change.

The Pre-production Stage

According to Ayushi Singh (2019), pre-production, also known as, prepress, is where photos are edited, advertisements are created and compared and the whole pages of the newspaper are laid out and designed after stories have been edited. Relatively, the editor and other sub-editor and other sub-editors will set in on editorial conference to determine what goes inside the paper for the day. Newspaper planning is the process of designing the layout of a newspaper on a mock-up sheet to stimulate the final look of each publication. The news pages are assembled in pre-production text using images, cutlines, graphics, and colors.

Meanwhile, Neil Kulkarni in 2018 points out that pre-production starts at the editorial meeting. According to him, pre-production is weekly for weekly papers and magazines, daily for daily papers and magazines, and monthly for monthly magazines. They essentially function as staff meetings where the editor, section editors, writers, and designers gather to discuss and debate what should be published in the paper/ magazine this day/ week/ month. The publisher may occasionally (rarely) be there, especially if the magazine or newspaper is running a special promotion or has a tie-in with a sponsor or product.

The newspaper pre-production process involves story selection, assigning journalists, research and fact-checking, writing and editing, and

layout and design (Antonia Phillips, 2019). While story selection is the phase where editors review the collected stories, prioritize them based on relevance and newsworthiness, and decide which ones to feature.

Assigning journalists to narrate or write news stories, reviews, or commentary for print, broadcast, or other communications media such as newspapers, magazines, radio, or television. Moreover, there is an assignment editor who assigns journalists to cover specific stories, providing guidelines, and instructions (Grace Smith, 2021).

Research and fact-checking refers to the pre-production stage where the journalists conduct further research, verify facts, and cross-check information (Brodsky et al., 2021).

The Production Stage

Writing and editing phase is where the journalists write articles following the newspaper's style guidelines, and editors review and edit the content (Truesdell, 2023).

According to Cian Murray (2022), news editing in journalism is when an individual assesses a piece of content and makes the necessary changes, ensuring the content is of the required standard. It is a complex process involving the assessment of news stories by an individual or team of individuals who did not write the story. News editors focus on the issues around spelling, grammar, and fact-checking and examine the readability of the content they are editing. Moreover, a news editor should have to condense a reporter's story for economy and space reasons.

News writing to journalistic writing that describes events by answering basic questions such as who, where, when, and why. In addition, news writing often requires some investigation on the part of the writer, which can include obtaining quotes or data to make the article as accurate and thorough as possible (Barron, 2022). Moreover, this type of writing is usually objective and expository, reporting and explaining the facts of an event rather than providing an opinion or analysis.

Layout design is the process of arranging visual and textual elements on-screen or on-paper in order to grab a reader's attention to communicate information in a visually appealing way. In addition, it is the process of arranging visual elements—like text, images, and shapes—on a given page. Layout design is important for any project that conveys a message through eye-catching visuals, like magazine layouts, website design, and advertisements (MasterClass, 2021).

Good layout design can have a massive impact on how any print or digital design is perceived. Where one is creating a printed brochure or a web app, a balanced page layout can ensure clear and effective communication and helps get the key messages across. And while it might seem that page layout is just about aesthetics, it can also have big practical consequences for usability, bounce rates, and conversions (Hampton-Smith, 2022).

The newspaper production comprises printing preparation, printing, proofreading, and packaging (Pandey, 20214). Printing preparation is when the final content and layout are prepared for printing, ensuring all elements are properly formatted. The printing stage refers to the newspaper files which were sent to the printing press, where the newspapers are printed using high-speed

printing machines. Proofreading is when a proofreader carefully views the entire newspaper for errors, typos, and layout inconsistencies. Packaging is when the printed newspapers are bundled, stacked, and prepared for distribution.

The Post-production Stage

The newspaper process as the last stage of publication of a newspaper refers to everything that takes place after the paper has been printed on parent sheets, which is quite a bit. The printed sheets will be folded, cut, and bound into the final project. This process involves inserting supplements, quality control, folding and trimming, and packaging and labeling (Bookblock, 2018). Inserting supplements or additional sections are inserted into the main newspapers. A quality control check is performed to ensure the newspapers meet the desired standards of print quality. Folding and Trimming is when the newspapers are packaged into bundles and labeled for easy identification.

With that being said, the distribution network plays a pertinent role in strengthening every newspaper organization. In time of delivery of newspapers to the destined readers is not an easy task. In newspaper distribution networks, the human factor plays a crucial role. In India, nearly 70% of the newspaper sales happen through door-to-door delivery through network agents (Hemalatha et al., 2018).

Synthesis

The different studies made by different scholars written here put up a clear idea which is the hundred pieces of importance of community media as well as the benefit of having it.

Since newspaper can feature dedicated pages promoting information worthy of reading, the community press can serve as a catalyst for change in addition to promoting local businesses and other related community development endeavors. One of the studies included here also states that the primary objective of a community newspaper or other small media outlet is to foster the development of an autonomous, interactive community. This is because, by reading content that is exclusive to the area, a person can gain knowledge that makes them feel a sense of belonging.

In contrary, similar with other traditional media, local or community-based publications still hurdle over challenges primarily on alleviating its financial support since these newsletters require certain amount of budget to continue its circulation. Additionally, manpower plays a huge role in establishing a paper as studies show that small publication finds it hard to form the editorial staff since most of the employees are not trained in journalism, which this kind of discipline is seen as a helping ground to solidify the accuracy and credibility of the paper. Hence, at the end of the day, despite changes in its medium, community newspapers are still a force that needs attention and good foundation in order to survive even when this medium started to adapt the demands of digitization.

Theoretical Framework

Media Ecology, led by Marshall McLuhan, is the study of different personal and social environments created by the use of different communication technologies. McLuhan claimed that changes to technology alter the human symbolic environment. Just as the age of literacy began to separate individuals, McLuhan saw the electronic age as re-tribalizing the human race. However, instead of small, isolated villages of the tribal age, people began to move towards becoming a connected, global village.

Contextually, this study can be understood through the lens of this theory, and it served as a ruling guide to understand the phenomenon of digital shift among traditional or printed newsletters. Due to pandemic, there are factors that need to be analyzed and the researcher attempted to shed light on that using the proposed idea of Media Ecology. Significantly, to understand the case of selected publications in Cavite, the researcher rooted the contributing factors of their decision to shift as well as the challenges encountered and their present situation due to the transformation the outside factors had created. Hence, this theory guided the researcher to explain the new environment that the editorial staff had found in the advent of technology and the researcher narratively presented how this digitization happened.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study that is anchored on the Media Ecology Theory by Marshall McLuhan.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

Marshall McLuhan's Media Ecology Theory plays an important role in this study as it further explains how traditional media evolves due to the demands of its environment which in this case, due to pandemic. McLuhan claimed that changes to technology alter human's symbolic environment. Just as the age of literacy began to separate individuals, McLuhan saw the electronic age as re-tribalizing the human race. However, instead of small,

isolated villages of the tribal age, people began to move towards becoming a connected, global village.

In accordance, with each new media that is adopted, sometimes the media creates more than it gets rid of. Other times it gets rid of more than it creates. Therefore, the end results are not always as profitable as it would have been to stay with the prior media. In this study, the researcher investigated this phenomenon as to how these publications emerged and transforming in a digital environment due to influential factors that only the informants can provide through their stories. Moreover, the researcher painstakingly analyzed through the media ecology theory the “past” and “present” or the *then* and *now* of each case to better understand the influential factor for their digitization.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research method, the key informants, data gathering procedure, and other items that further explain the study.

Research Design

The researcher used a Case Study Approach. This qualitative research approach focuses on answering “how” and “why” questions. One of the advantages of this approach is the close collaboration between the researcher and the participant, while enabling participants to tell their stories. Through these stories the participants are able to describe their views of reality, and this enables the researcher to better understand the participant’s actions.

Accordingly, the study aimed to seek, describe, and explain the phenomenon of community media transformation and its changing nature. It was made possible by collecting information through structured questions in a form of an in-depth interview participated by the head of selected community newsletters in Cavite who experienced transformation made by the demands of digital environment.

Informants of the Study

The informants who were interviewed by the researcher were the head or the editor-in-chief of selected municipalities in Cavite. They were chosen since they have an established newspaper or newsletter and they can give pieces of information on the transformation that the community media went

through. Their participation is highly significant since the researcher attempted to explain the underlying issues in relation to their experience when they underwent digitization.

Sampling Procedure

To get the informants, the researcher focused on purposive sampling and set the criteria to determine those who will be qualified for an interview. The informant must be knowledgeable with the transition of their paper from traditional to digital therefore, the researcher targeted the heads or the editors-in-chief who have been serving their community for more than years already. Hence, these informants are also the ones who are tasked to lead their constituents in terms of news and information dissemination.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher began the study by thickening supporting facts such as related literature and other books that are helpful to fully understand the topic of this research as well as to determine the gap.

Secondly, the researcher visited all the municipalities in Cavite and sent a request letter to humbly investigate those who have an existing community newsletter/ newspaper. The request was given along with the letter of intent.

After the selection process, for the researcher to underscore the main problems, the researcher sent another request letter among the informants with an attached interview guide and informed consent to explain their rights and roles in fulfilling the objectives of this study.

Research Instrument

The researcher asked the permission of the target participants through an informed consent which was given to them, and it discussed the method of data gathering and their right to withdraw from the interview. Thus, a copy of interview guide questions was sent to them prior to the scheduled interview. The interview guide questions consist of several parts.

The first part revolves around the editorial background and it includes the name of publication, date of establishment of the publication, and length of publication.

The next part is formulated to highlight their stories as to how they manage their community in this digital environment in terms of media ownership, budget allocation, and manpower. This is important to ask as it elucidates a comparison between the previous and current media that they have.

The last section is intended to explain the production process followed by the distribution process of the community media. These two parts provided a clear idea of digital shift and how community media in Cavite transformed over the years.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher guaranteed the strict confidentiality of the information and all ethical issues in the study were addressed properly.

First, the researcher informed the key informants about the objectives and significance of the study as well as the procedures of the in-depth interview. Relatedly, in order to gather the data, the researcher provided a self-made

questionnaire which was validated by three (3) experts in the field of study. After the preparation, the questionnaire was administered to the participants. Participation on the study was voluntary and may be terminated if the participants wish to do so. The personal information of every participant was kept in a highly confidential manner.

Furthermore, the researcher retrieved the data personally to ensure confidentiality. There were no risks and discomforts in the study because the researcher only asked questions written on the questionnaire and no personal or sensitive issues were tackled. Afterwards, the gathered data underwent transcription using a coding guide to identify themes which were used in the discussion of result. All gathered data was kept between the participants and researcher including the advisory committee for research purposes only.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result from the in-depth interview is presented in this chapter to explain the changing nature of community media or the case as to how it is transforming in the digital environment. The following themes emerged from the method of analysis and were used to discuss the “*then*” and “*now*” of the four (4) newsletters and one (1) newspaper in the province of Cavite.

In accordance with the data gathering procedure, the following publications in Cavite were identified and each head participated with proper consent to help the researcher understand the background and how they shifted digitally.

Selected Publications in the Province of Cavite

Municipality of Indang

Based on the researcher’s initial attempt to discover the existence of community media, it was discovered that this municipality had produced several information outlets in the past. In an interview with one of the founders of an online newspaper in Indang, there were two sources of information that have been established before. The first one is *Indang.org* (a premier source of online news and information) which is a local online newspaper that started in 2009 in preparation for the 2010 election.

According to the informant, the main goal of their newspaper is to become the primary source of information for the betterment of Indang. Since they started as an independent media outlet in preparation of the said election, one of their editorial policies was basically avoiding any political sorties. They

launched in May right after the said election, and one of their breaking news is the coverage of the lost blessed sacrament in Indang. Another huge coverage of their online newspaper is when they managed to report the oath taking of Congressman Boying Remulla through webcasting and they had hundreds of views on that certain live webcast. Part also of their main goal is to educate the people of Indang on the importance of their culture and tradition by reporting the “Indang Day Celebration” which was also live and viewed all throughout their web page. Through their newspaper, they also had the chance to tackle and discuss special events such as Andres Bonifacio Day and other events that are worth celebrating. Aside from all these achievements, one great thing that their newspaper has done according to Mojica is they made a social relevance in the community. They successfully came up with *“Kwaderno Para sa Batang Indangenyoy”* wherein they were able to distribute 5,000 notebooks in two weeks. Hence, the notebooks were distributed through different barangays particularly to less fortunate children in grade 1 and 2 within Indang.

However, one of their difficulties in establishing a news portal in Indang is the idea that weekly news is not always present and since they were considered as an independent group, getting funds became a problem in sustaining the portal.

Moreover, the content of Indang.org is not just news, but it also has sections such as special events, Frequently Ask Questions (FAQs), information of different barangay and its chairpersons. They are not supplying as much news as they can since they only have a few workers in their online paper. Prior to that, one of their strategies they did to make their page successful and become known is when they partnered with different computer shops around

Indang where those computer owners agreed to change all their computer wallpapers into *Indang.page*'s official image. The informant furthered that they also had trouble sustaining it due to lack of resources in terms of workers and money.

Trece Martires City

Trece Martires' newsletter started in 2013 and already had two consecutive names before "MDS Newsletter." MDS stands for the initials of Mayor Melandrez de Sagun, and consequently, the fourth-class municipality's slogan "*Moving Directly to Success*". The name has been discussed and finalized by the Tourism Council.

Based on an interview with the administrative aide and one of the heads of the MDS newsletter, its establishment was mobilized by their will to have a newspaper they can call their own. The newsletter merely started because they really need a newspaper to inform the community regarding the latest updates or upcoming projects of the Mayor. Its publication is supported by the local government through the tourism office thus budget has never been an issue to them. The informant added that they do not need much budget since the basic materials they need to create their paper are bond papers and scotch tape only.

The situation of MDS newsletter in terms of budget fell in the study written in *The Rise and Fall of Philippine Community Newspapers* by Crispin Maslog that explained "newspaper funding comes from the owners, with little expectation from the profit since most local papers do not cost that much" (Maslog, 1993).

Aside from the official newsletter, they also managed to make an online portal namely *lgu.trecemartirez@blogspot* wherein news written in their paper can also be browsed.

Meanwhile, it was also revealed in the interview that the members of the staff were chosen according to the hierarchy or the organizational structure of their division wherein the Mayor serves as the chairman of the paper and the rest of the editorial board comes from the Tourism Office. There are also contributors in the Mayor's office, but initially, the informant is one of the three heads who manages the paper. In addition, there has been a publisher before, but they decided not to include her in the paper anymore since she was no longer a government employee. One requirement to become eligible in their paper is he or she must be a government employee.

A lot of problems and difficulties were seen in many studies related to community newspapers in the Philippines. For the LGU of Trece Martires City, the main problem encountered was in news gathering. According to Masigla, gathering of information has been a huge dilemma for them because there are other institutions that always fail to submit a report even if they give deadlines. There is also lack in manpower as Masigla is the only person who gathers news for the newsletter.

Municipality of Silang

One of the oldest newsletters that still exists in Cavite is the *Arengkadang Balita* ng Silang founded by its former The Manila Times reporter who also serves as the editor and publisher of this seven-year-old newsletter. Similar to Trece Martires, it got its name from the Mayor of Silang. The informant

is one of those owners who chose individual type of ownership, using his journalistic skills as a veteran reporter and own initiative. Having understood the need of Silang for a newspaper, he volunteered as its editor in 2009 and produced 5,000 copies of newsletter for the sake of the community. Unlike Trece Martires, Silang was able to produce large number of copies as a starting point. The opportunity to circulate such number was made possible because local papers like this have the tendency to be “financially stable” since it is relatively small (Maslog, 1993).

However, it was mentioned in the interview that the main costing of the paper depends on the number of copies. The initial costing relies on *pre-press*. Pre-press is where planning of building the paper starts, involving transportation expenses for news gathering.

He also added that newspaper nowadays can easily be produced because of the digitization period. A writer no longer needs to manually type a story. Now that computer with a spellchecker has dominated the press, it does not require most of the writer’s time except if the medium is Tagalog. He emphasized that community newspaper should use Filipino as a writing medium but cited that “Taglish” will do.

Arengkadang Balita ng Silang does not contain any negative stories and opinion column section since Lolo Totsi patronizes “development journalism”.

As an individual owner, he still looks for ways to produce an outcome that will not affect the quantity. Based on the observation though, the quality has diminished especially the appearance since the newsletter went from colored type to a cheaper merely black and white.

Imus City

This former municipality is the youngest publication among the publications that were already mentioned. This city is managing a government-owned newspaper magazine called *BANAAG* and has an online outlet as well.

Carmona City

This magazine type of publication has been circulating from almost eleven (11) years now. Like in Bacoor, it began as an annual report of the accomplishments of the city of Carmona. This local paper is supported by their Mayor and Php300,000.00 is the allocated budget for every 5,000 copies each year. It was observed as the second to the highest number of copies among the aforementioned papers. Hence, the main factor this city considered in establishing their paper is the need of their Mayor in order to bring out all the term agenda.

Samyo can be received throughout Carmona specifically in schools and barangays. And since they also wanted to circulate the paper outside their city, they made an idea to keep it inside their personalized eco-bag along with their product so visitors from other places can read the said magazine.

Part 1.1 The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Media Ownership*

Varied Ownership

In the past, based on the analysis derived from the in-depth interview with the informants, there are two (2) kinds of media ownership in the past. Three (3) of them are owned by the Local Government Unit (LGU) while the other is a privately owned newspaper.

“Nagsimula talaga kami sa scratch... ‘yung printed media namin. Inalam namin kung paano magiging effective saka pa’no mae-engage ‘yung Imuseños sa pagbabasa ng news. Saka ano... kung pa’no ma-desseminate ‘yung newsletters nang maayos.” – Informant 2

“At my own initiative ‘to eh. Walang inutos ang Mayor, hindi pa man ako empleyado, nag-issue ako ng 5,000 copies, nakatuwaan, sabi sa akin ituloy na. At ‘yon, hindi ‘yon every month, every two months or three months... tuwing kelan ko gusto lumabas.” – Informant 3

When the COVID-19 pandemic struck, the three newsletters that belonged to the LGU continued to publish despite the physical limitations imposed by the virus's threat and for the employees' safety. With cooperation from the municipal office, the publication made the relatively easy decision to use the available medium which is online media. It was discovered that despite change that these publications underwent; their media ownership remained the same as majority of them are still owned by the local government.

Accordingly, in order to better serve their constituents, these newsletters have adopted a statist approach which is made feasible by the type of ownership indicated.

In connection on how these publications started their e-newsletter, formal consultation in accordance with digital convergence was made. The informants stated that they had to go through a formal consultation with their mayor prior to deciding to digitally transition from their traditional method of publication. However, one publication took a different path because the person in charge of the paper works alone and did not take the municipal office's assistance into consideration. Accordingly, one municipality started developing their website and social media account even before the pandemic to create a backup plan that would meet the demands of their residents.

“Parang nu’ng ni-release ‘yung publication na printed, the end of 2016, in-activate na rin ‘yung social media account tapos ‘yung website pinaayos ko na rin by 2017.” – Informant 1

“ ‘Pag government kasi dapat ‘yung mga newsletter nila available any time sa may gusto. Tapos para ma-secure namin ‘yung papel, we make sure na it is released only through the official sites and pages ng Imus... tapos dapat may proper branding and included din dapat ‘yung names ng employees na involved sa paggawa.” – Informant 2

The informants believe that social media management is essential for navigating the digital landscape and distributing information. Their narratives also provide adequate support that in shifting digitally, a publication must consider proper branding since one needs to ensure the audience’s familiarity and at the same time through social media management, the community media preserves their editorial accountability.

Part 1.2 The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Budget Allocation*

Reportedly Decreasing

Though it was mentioned in the interview that in the past, their paper deals with lesser financial allocation, important aspects of budgeting were also declared during the interview. It was explained that budget was the first thing that a municipality considers before establishing a newspaper or any type of publication and it is also a basic need.

One of the publications said in the interview that the initial costing of pre-establishment of a local paper is usually invested in printing and transportation especially in gathering and distribution of news. Though it has not stated the exact amount of money in the in-depth interview since it depends on the income of the municipality, the number of copies they want to produce should also be

considered as one of the important needs since it will oversee how much budget they must allocate. In a simpler context, revenue helps the organization work. It supports the company as well as the people involved in a certain service. Considering revenue in a newspaper organization is very vital because doing a newspaper job needs a lot of money and investment (Soriano, 1999).

“Ang costing nyan, depende sa number of copies. Habang dumadami, lumalaki presyo. Pero ‘dun sa first thousand, ‘pag sa imprenta ka pupunta, ‘yung first one thousand bibigyan ka nila kagad ng rate. Ang gastos kagad ‘yung running.

Okay, ito talaga ang mga gastos, una ‘yung pre-press, ‘yung paggather ng information, you’ll use gasoline... mag-i-interview ka, mama-masahe ka. Pagkuha ng litrato, ‘di kamukha nung araw, ngayon digital na. . . papa-print mo nalang. ‘Yun ang initial costing, ‘yun ang pre-press.” – Informant 3

Meanwhile, one municipality survived three (3) years of not having an estimated budget from their Mayor and only materials such as bond paper, scotch tape, and printer were used to produce 200 copies each month.

“Wala syang ano... budget, kasi... hmm kasi ang ano lang namin ay bond paper, ‘yung mga tape na ginagamit namin. Lahat sa budget na ng tourism.” – Informant 4

Going back in the case of the privately owned publication, although their community newspaper is individually owned, they still managed to circulate 500-1,000 copies that cost Php1,000.00 only since their Mayor agreed to support the newsletter by providing the needed paper just to lessen the printing cost. While in one municipality, a more expensive paper is distributed given the socio-economic status of the city and the number of copies they circulate annually. It is the same with the idea of the other head explaining that the income of municipality and its socio-economic status affect the income for the establishment of paper.

Relatively, as an individual owner, he still looks for ways to produce an outcome that will not affect the quantity. Based on the observation though, the quality has diminished, especially the appearance since the newsletter went from colored type to a cheaper merely black and white.

In summary, it was noticed that the budget should be met first. According to study, one publication cannot rely on public's patronage alone. Community newspapers must be continuously funded for them to survive (Soriano & Vergara, 2013). This study also explained the probable cause why these set of publications in Cavite still exist.

In addition, three municipalities clearly said they started publishing because of one single mission, to utilize the paper and make it as a report of the accomplishments they made. This also answers the question why they are still capable of circulating despite the large amount of budget because their mission is supported and eventually it became their source/s of budget. Soriano and Vergara (2013) said in their research, that local politicians often utilize these newspapers to advance their agenda which helps the community newspaper survive. That is why purpose is also a need to be considered even in the digital environment.

As for the financial support the moment they transitioned, all the newsletters except for Silang are **co-dependent to their office**. Three (3) of them are funded by the LGU while the other one is individually strategic. Even before and up until now that they already shifted in a digital environment, these community media are supported by the LGU in terms of managing their finances.

“...may budget kasi kami for PIO namin, ‘yung Public Information Officer, under din ng Office of the Mayor. So, doon, meron kaming allotted budget para sa ganyan na kinukuhanan namin.” – Informant 1

In contrast, the case of one of the publications involved in this study is similar to the study conducted by Dr. Maslog in 1993. Community newspapers, sometimes called local newspapers, are usually family-owned. Being relatively small, these local papers have the tendency to be “financially stable” (Maslog, 1993). Initially, funding comes from the owners, with little expectation from the profit since most local papers do not cost that much.

Based on the analysis of their cases, a noticeable change they encountered is the fact that when they shifted, online media offers minimal allocation of budget resulting in cheaper expenses. Also, according to them, social media is a free platform except for Website since the municipality needs to pay for its domain. Overall, the digitized version of their publication made the budget preparation easier. Hence, it helped the traditional publication experience a smooth change or transition in a digital environment and it did not prohibit the service to the community.

“...itong sa social media, wala rin naman tayo... kumbaga free naman siya. ‘Yung website, ‘yung official website kasi binabayaran namin ‘yung domain, ‘yung hosting. So, ayun ‘yung mga technical aspect na kailangan mong bayaran. Nababayaran naman namin sya. Subscription kumbaga. Kasi kailangan mo ‘yung domain no’n na binibili mo, ‘yung www.lndang.ph.” – Informant 1

“Sa ngayon... du’n sa digitized version ng newsletter namin, it made it easier to comply with the required papers for budget preparation. Kaso, we are still producing the same number of printed copies as before, considering the budget allocation that we receive annually. We also usually have more copies during the first half of the year.” – Informant 2

Part 1.3 The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Manpower*

Less Staff Needed

According to the narrative shared by the informants, most of them explained that there was an **imbalance during work assignments or designation** due to the number of employees in their office in the past. It was also revealed that back then, most of their editorial staff were not trained in journalism.

“ ‘yun nga ang naging challenge kaya hindi na siya na-revive, ‘yung printed version. Kasi do’n mo mari-realize na talagang kailangan mo ng isang entity sa ganitong institution na parang media. Meron ka rin talaga for PR saka na media dapat na team. Kasi ang nangyari no’n kumuha lang ako per department ng contributors... ng mga empleyado. So, from agriculture kukuha ka ng isa. Tapos from sa anong department, kung sino man na ano, kukuha ka lang.” – Informant 1

One of the vital needs a certain municipality must also consider is the group of people or the editorial board. In the interview, most of them chose employees from the Public Information Office and the rest are from the Tourism Office. One informant explained that often municipalities ask for the help of PIO since they are already capable of doing jobs related to information dissemination.

The problem with the high cost of the production process, specifically printing, was seen as a main hindrance in hiring full-time reporters. The owners of some community newspapers rely mainly on press releases or free updates from local government agencies which makes their content “written in the same perspective” (Soriano & Vargas, 2013).

According to Maslog (1993), most editorial staff of community newspapers also lack training and experience prior to entering the publications. In a study

conducted by Jerry Yapo and Alexandra Cabrera on community journalism in Southern Tagalog, aside from production issues and other external constraints, some community newspapers also problematize inadequacy of editorial staff which includes “lack of sufficient editorial staff, lack of journalistic skills and experience, and lack of professional education and training” (Cabrera & Yapo, 1990).

When it comes to the comparison of staff from then and now, majority of the informants observed a lesser manpower now that they are working in a digital environment.

“Yung sa social media ang gumagawa lang ako... ako lang ang nag-a approve. Minsan ako na rin ang naggagawa ng write up. Tapos may isa akong staff na gano'n din, minsan papa-check nya sa'kin, sya 'yung gagawa ng write up... mabilis.” – Informant 1

Moreover, employees from the Tourism Office were singled out as the target ones to comprise the editorial staff. One informant added that the Mayor could be the head of their paper. He also expressed willingness to take charge of the desired community-based paper if the situation calls for it. According to study, the manpower of community newspapers is generally smaller as compared to the national newspapers, apparently because it only serves a specific community. Since there is a problem financially, media organizations in community just hire journalists who will be assigned or just take a certain task. Thus, it is not surprising to encounter community-based print publication that has only one or two people who do all the work (Arao, 2010).

Due to the demand of the task, the editorial board back then decided to choose employees from other offices who are knowledgeable or have direct concern with a particular topic. According to the interview, it was also mentioned that some writers back then were referred.

“Usually, du’n sa department na concern. ‘Pag culture, ang ano niyan... tourism. Tapos depende kung meron kaming resource person coming from another department. Halimbawa meron dito do’n sa assessor, nu’ng nabubuhay pa ‘yung dating boss naming, si Sir Chito... so, marami syang connection, marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling ‘yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.” – Informant 1

“...ang nilagay lang namin sa parang... kami talaga sa tourism, kaming tatlo lang ‘yun sa editorial, parang contribution ‘yung mga staffs ng Mayor’s office... ‘yung mga matataas sa Mayor’s office. Katulad nung admin, ‘yung senior executive assistant, ‘yung EA saka ‘yung EA1 and 2.

The past scenario experienced by the publications involved in this study where most of the writers and staff took the task despite lack of relevant training had a similar occurrence to what Dr. Maslog discovered in 1993. According to him, a good number of editors had their informal training upon experience as time passed by and although most of them do not necessarily have degree in Journalism, they were still hired to work for these community newspapers (Maslog, 1993).

In accordance, the study shows that there was an obvious difference between role selection in the past and the present or apparent change in the designation of tasks in the present is evident. It was mainly due to the wide selection of topics. Now that they shifted digitally, it became easier to tap writers who will produce the online content especially that their source had widen online.

Topics such as Holiday event and matters related to it became apparent and easy to disseminate now that guidelines are easily accessible at home through world wide web. Compared in the past, it is no longer difficult to assign the task online.

“Oo, meron pa rin kaming gano’n. Usually gano’n ‘yung tina-tap namin. Actually, ngayon mas lumaki kasi minsan meron kaming mga articles or kagaya ng Bonifacio Day... ‘yung celebration ng Bonifacio Day. Meron kaming sarili pero minsan kumukuha kami ng info from National Government—Philippine Information Agency.” – Informant 1

Part 2.1 The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Production Process*

A. Content Gathering

News and Information Planning Made Easy

It was recorded that news planning was much easier in the past and before transitioning to digital media, there is an established system such as a regular meeting to discuss the structure of their newsletter.

“Nagpapatawag ako ng meeting tapos parang ginawan ko sya ng organizational chart. Kumbaga direction, naka-flow chart ‘yung articles, ‘yung pinaka-structure ng newsletter. So, meron kaming main feature, ito ‘yung tungkol sa mandate ni Mayor, ‘yung ginagawa nya tapos meron kang mga articles do’n na naka-focus sa history, sa environment, sa tourism, culture... so, nakagano’n lang sya.” – Informant 2

“Noon kasi, usually, may regular meeting kami noon. Madali. Kumbaga andu’n na ‘yung pinakaano mo, du’n ka lang mag-iisip kung ano’ng ipapasok mong articles.” – Informant 1

Interestingly, from an individual ownership perspective, the head of one of the publications mentioned that it was also challenging to package the community newspaper mainly because he did all the work by himself. The informant also emphasized the importance of *pre-press*. Pre-press is where

planning of building the paper starts, involving transportation expenses for news gathering.

He is also aware that newspapers nowadays can easily be produced because of the digitization period. A writer is no longer pressured to manually type a story. Now that a computer with a spellchecker has dominated the press, it does not require most of the writer's time except if the medium is Tagalog. He emphasized that community newspaper should use Filipino as a writing medium but cited that "*Taglish*" will do.

"Nung araw, type talaga, tapos dadalhin mo sa printing. . . ngayon may computer na, may spell check pa. Maliban nalang kung Tagalog. Ang community paper should be Tagalog. Lalo na't Cavite. 'Wag kayong maglalagay ng Ingles, pwede mag-taglish... wala masyadong nagbabasa ng Ingles." – Informant 3

Schroder's study conducted in 2019 further enriches the discussion by identifying four specific profiles of news interest, highlighting the diversity of audience preferences. This insight complements the editorial team's task of satisfying diverse community needs through a comprehensive analysis of issues. While Schroder recommends that journalists follow their instincts and prioritize stories with civic value, the editorial process outlined in the discussion provides a tangible framework for achieving this by aligning news coverage with community-specific topics and needs.

Before the digitization happened and when there was no disruption on physical movement, one of the informants explained that designation of beat is much easier in the past since they normally tap the concerned office which can expertly provides the topic being asked. One example is in the case of the

newsletter of Indang wherein topics involving culture are packaged and cared of under the Tourism Office. In accordance, they also welcome experts from other departments who can potentially serve as resource people for a particular article.

“Usually, du’n sa department na concern. ‘Pag culture, ang ano niyan... tourism. Tapos depende kung meron kaming resource person coming from another department. Halimbawa meron dito do’n sa assessor, nu’ng nabubuhay pa ‘yung dating boss naming, si Sir Chito... so, marami syang connection, marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling ‘yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.” – Informant 1

Beat designation plays a huge role in establishing a community press. In most cases, it foresees the potential of the paper to provide solutions or other development initiatives. A study in India that the community press helped to promote literature and science through the dissemination of knowledge among the uneducated masses by reading and discussion of essays and literary, historical, and social subjects, by lectures on physical and chemical science accompanied by experiments, and by the publication of cheap monthly periodical literature suited to the requirements and tastes of the people (Parikh, 1951). Therefore, it is beneficial that in any community-based media, beat assignment is well-planned and receives an equal amount of attention.

Concisely, the discussion and Schroder’s study collectively promote the holistic approach to journalism. The editorial process is not only about identifying relevant topics and needs but also figuring out the challenges of media competition, all while prioritizing stories that resonate on a personal level and hold substantial civic value as it ensures a more informed, engaged, and connected community through the careful selection and presentation of news content.

In the idea of setting up interviews in the past compared to the present condition, there was no drastic change in terms of adapting to the demands of digital environment therefore, ethical gathering of human source is evident in the present. Still, based on the interview, finding appropriate human source is a must and setting up interview including request must be conducted first then and now.

“Meron kami, ‘yung pinaka-interview na kinonduct is during newsletter time. ‘Yung printed. Kasi do’n nga, ang nangyari sa kanya ay para syang magazine type e. Kagaya no’n, ‘yung pinakamatandang magkalamay sa Indang ininterview. So, pati ‘yon naghanap sila ng mga resource person do’n na magbibigay ng story tungkol sa ano ng kalamay. – Informant 1

“We usually set up an interview by sending a request letter or a memo to the office or employees involved with the program or project.” – Informant 2

The study findings were related to the literature authored by Taylor (2016) which revolves around advice for beat reporters who are establishing connections and interactions with the sources that they will be using and being prepared with the information regarding their background of their sources as it has an impact on their understanding of what to expect with the content of their topics.

To come to a point, the insight of Taylor highlights the importance of preparedness, understanding and structured engagement for effective beat reporting.

In a clearer perspective considering the changing nature of community media in a digital environment, the findings solidify that it is much easier to find content using social media. In comparison, content gathering was more tedious in the past since the staff needed to gatekeep or provide physical copies for logistics purposes.

“...we connect with different offices... tapos ‘yung mga researchers namin, they verify muna the contents they gathered before giving the details to the writer saka pa nila ipo-post or print for public consumption.” – Informant 2

Relatively, both in the past and present had one thing in common. The newspaper still needs to do proper research and that involves verifying facts. Hence, whether the content is easier to locate online, the publication must hold on to the principle of accuracy to keep their paper’s integrity.

Writing a story in the newsroom might be challenging if there is little data to work with. Because of this, gathering information for a news item is essential before starting to write one (Rogers, 2019). The information will form the basis of the story and assist in ensuring that no important details are overlooked (Posner, 2023), leading to a more cohesive framework for one's work. Verifying the information in every news story is a crucial step to avoid spreading false information.

In the digital age, information spreads so swiftly that false and misleading information is becoming widespread. In the discipline of journalism, it is pivotal to provide authentic news and information to the public by ensuring that every detail of the content has been verified and fact-checked numerous times. In that way, the community media can repel fallacies.

Moreover, when verifying the authenticity of secondary sources for a news article, it is crucial to consider the information's provenance or origin, the person who created the account where the information is found, the publication date, the location where it was published, and the purpose of the website or source (Urbani, 2019). These factors will ensure the credibility of the secondary source for each story.

In the end, although traditional content gathering is meticulously managed in the past, the functions of the community media in terms of information dissemination even in the digital environment remains the same and true to its vision. The community media should provide accurate sources of news and information to the community whether it is an actual print or a digital copy.

Part 2.2. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Production Process*

B. Content Packaging

Based on the interview, one of the publications does not contain any negative stories and opinion column section since its head patronizes “development journalism.” Thus, the EIC serves their municipality by giving free newsletter to his fellow men and he is recognized by the mayor. Due to this, he said that he does not need other writers to help him.

“...‘Pag ka community paper, puro magaganda, pagka ‘yung Tabloid style naman, may investigative reporting, pero pag ka community newspaper... puro magagandang balita ng komunidad. ‘Di kamukha ng mga newspaper dito sa Cavite, merong mga binibira. ‘Yung dyaryo ko dito eh... community newspaper na walang pangit na balita. Kasi aral ako kay Marcos... ‘yung developmental information. Before Martial Law reporter na ako ng *The Manila Times*, ‘nung mag-martial law, syempre susunod ka, puro magandang balita lang.” – Informant 3

Meanwhile, sunshine journalism or pieces of information that are solely positive were evident in the way of writing among other publications involved in this study.

Aside from unchanged editing and lay-outing procedure both in the past and present, it was revealed that there was an unequal distribution of editing and lay-outing task and this content packaging aspect was another challenge among informants. One of the difficulties they face each year according to the head of one publication is the inability of the contributors to submit their assigned draft on time which causes publishing delays. This certain instance added to so-called “production constraints” frequently problematized by local newspapers (Ingles & Maceda, 1981). Aside from high costs of printing and supplies, as well as the lack of printing equipment, manpower is also the primary problem often cited. Thus, power interruptions are also a problem especially if it is frequent and results in costly production delays (Ingles & Maceda, 1981).

Luckily, despite not having their own printing press and often relying on a private maker, one advantage they shared is they have an artist who layouts the paper. It is seen as a good strategy since “layout stage” is one of the time-consuming parts of production. And if the staff are not knowledgeable about this, the help of a layout artist can somehow make their job less hassle.

Unfortunately, it was a different case for the other newsletter because according to the interview, in terms of editing and lay-outing, all the tasks in this process were carried out by the EIC alone even before they shifted to digital newsletter. It was mainly because he found it cost efficient to use his skills in creative industry where he came from and at the same time, it is difficult for him to entrust the work of editing to anyone who does not have any background experience with the aforementioned task.

“...ako na rin. Kasi nga ‘yun ‘yung trabaho ko e. Nag-art director ako... creative director ako ng agency... creative agency. Mostly talaga, sa design talaga ang trabaho ko. Sa creative. ‘Yun ‘yung ginagamit ko. Kaya minsan talaga, kahit nu’ng time ng COVID, ‘yun na ‘yung... wala akong maasahan e. ‘Yan ‘yang mga ‘yan, ‘yang mga Indang Atin ‘To na mga yan... ako gumagawa nyan. Kasi nga wala ka ditong makukuhang tao. Na ‘yung sa discipline mo or galing sa industry mo na meron dito. Mahirap. Bihira. So, talagang tyatyagain mo sya. ‘Yun ‘yung challenge ng pagdya-dyaryo.” – Informant 1

This explains that community media, both in traditional and digital environment, requires critical attention in editing and lay-outing to achieve an effective frame that will cater to the needs of different audiences.

In terms of visual appeal and content presentation in a digital environment, based on the interview with the informants, it was found out that there were observed challenges such as lack of creativity resulting to unsatisfied readers when they shifted to digital community media.

“Kumbaga ano, hindi sila... ‘yun nga number one hindi gano’n ka-sharpen ‘yung creativity. So, kumbaga parang sila, kung ano lang ‘yung info, as is. Pero hindi nila ire-relay na parang storytelling.” – Informant 1

“Sa challenge, siguro kapag hindi satisfied ‘yung readers namin tapos mga taga-Imus pa talaga sila. Since, our task is to deliver information to the public katulad ng programs, projects, and updates sa local government ng Imus, ginagawa talaga namin ‘yung best namin para ma-fact-check saka ma-verify bawat details na nari-receive namin.”

It shows that there is still fear on the end of each publication despite experiencing change in a digital environment because according to them, they still need to secure the image branding, quality of photos, timeliness, etcetera

of each post for them to serve their people and maintain a good consumer's participation for their online newsletter to keep alive.

Part 3.1 The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of *Distribution Process*

A. Medium or Outlet

More Convenient Dissemination

There are two existing platforms for their community media (printed and newsletter and digital). In the past, their paper was described to have a more luxurious output due to paper type which is glossy or the magazine type.

"...yung paper nya hindi 'yung newspaper type. 'Yung glossy. Ang ginamit naming no'n is 'yung C2S na Wanted pa yata. Basta 'yung pang-page ng magazine. 'yung glossy na coated tapos back-to-back 'yon pero isang page lang sya na malaki e na size ng newspaper pero kapag hinawakan mo sya glossy sya." – Informant 1

"We have produced print and digital copies of the newsletter before the pandemic. Hanggang ngayon kasi meron pa rin kami." – Informant 2

Based on the conducted interview, when these local papers changed in a digital environment, online releases became more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce.

"...itong sa social media, wala rin naman tayo... kumbaga free naman siya." – Informant 1

"Of course, digital is more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce e. However, we still encourage the public to read the paper through the physical document given to them; thus, we display these in every office as much as possible." – Informant 2

Misinformation, Photo Stealing, and Underemployment. As for the challenge of transforming their medium and realigning it with the demands of a digital environment, it was discovered that misinformation is prevalent and improper grabbing of photos was seen. According to one of the informants, it was also mentioned that one of the challenges he encountered is working with a staff who was unfit for the description, but he did not have a choice because of manpower issues.

“ ‘Yun nga medyo mababa ‘yung creativity na hindi mo naman pwede paghanapan sila kasi sasabihin nila, “Hindi naman namin trabaho ‘yan.” So, ‘yun ‘yung mga aspect na ‘pag galing ka sa ano tapos gusto mong magkaro’n ng... mag-materialize ‘yung concept na ginagamit mo sa ibang industry na ilalagay mo rito, so, pipigain mo talaga sila. Mahihirapan ka. So, maraming trabaho on your part. Kumbaga sa’kin o kung dalawa lang kaming nakakaintindi halos kami lahat ‘yung umaayos. So, kumbaga ‘yung makukuha mo lang sa kanila ay piling pili lang. – Informant 1

Issues such as the one stated supports the fact that manpower of community newspapers is generally smaller as compared to the national newspapers, apparently because it only serves a specific community. Since there is a problem financially, media organizations in community just hire journalists who will be assigned or just take a certain task. Thus, it is not surprising to encounter community-based print publication that has only one or two people who do all the work (Arao, 2010).

It was also mentioned during the interview that since the municipality of Indang was experiencing financial constraint due to pandemic, instead of hiring another personnel, the head decided to do the task on his own. It proves that one of the changing natures of community media in a digital environment is the **adaptability of its staff to remain resilient in times where lack of**

manpower is evident in order to continue persevering for the sake of information dissemination.

B. Frequency of Releasing

Quickly Disseminating

Informants had a common takeaway when asked about their experience when they were still releasing their paper before the pandemic. One of the informants said that it was a fulfilling experience for them to see the actual fruit of their hard work. Meanwhile, informant 3 considered their way of releasing back then as an opportunity to freely manage the paper solely. Hence, the interview revealed that releasing their paper regardless of the frequency of release including resources needed is not a problem.

“Sa department na kami namigay noon eh, tapos nilalagay nalang namin ‘to sa main information (desk) dyan, tapos ‘yung iba dina-direct dito kapag kailangan ng mga students.” – Informant 4

“Namimigay kame sa mga barangays at schools, syempre for free ‘yun.” – Informant 5

On the other hand, it was also discovered that packaging the materials is more difficult than releasing an issue.

Accordingly, in navigating in the digital environment, one of the informants said that it is much better now that they have shifted digitally.

“One of the challenges of releasing an issue back then was the delay in printing. Also, events dated during the last week of the month would require some time for writers, editors, and proofreaders to produce articulated articles. May times na nae-

experience pa rin namin pero mas better na ngayon kasi digital media na.” – Informant 2

Meanwhile, according to informant 5, there is a minimal delay now. Also, releasing an issue in a digital environment paved way to faster news and information dissemination since social media offers a fast venue and serves as a reliable platform for their aforementioned initiatives. Lastly, information for the community became easier especially for those who have constant access to the internet.

The result of the interview also acknowledged the disadvantages at present such as smaller opportunity, digital divide, and lack of skills now that these community media changed and currently navigating in the digital environment. Relatively, social media offers same routine unlike in printed newsletter wherein the publication needs to conduct planning.

“Ang magiging ano mo... social media... may tendency ka na parang iisa lang ‘yung magiging flow ng ano mo... kasi sanay kana e. Kumbaga usual alam mo na ‘pag si Mayor umikot, ‘pag may mga event... parang paulit-ulit lang naman. Unlike sa newsletter nga talagang pinag-iisipan.” – Informant 1

This disadvantage may impose a threat to the ideal nature of community media which is to facilitate the process of negotiating and making meaning about community. In this sense, due to the fast-paced nature of social media, if proper planning through meeting is neglected, there is a tendency that it could result to convoluted posts rather than well-thought issues and information concerning the community (Lowrey, 2008).

Moreover, according to informant 2, they saw the current appearance and new outlet due to the changing nature of community media as a factor as

to why people are sometimes confused. Based on his statement, not every resident has the capability and time to check the official social media page of their city.

As for the other informant, members of their publication must innovate as well due to the changing nature of their paper. Particularly, members of their publication had to undergo training due to lack of skills in digital media.

This explains that despite the changing nature of community media in a digital environment, aside from investing on skills enhancement program or project, the publication must never forget that finding ways on how to provide information to the audience in an easy and effective way must not be forgotten since according to the study, the continuous publication of community newspapers suggests that the industry is not dead, contrary to the notion that the modernization of the media like digitization will kill the print medium. Perhaps the purpose of the community newspapers makes them strong and alive (Soriano & Vergara, 2013).

Community newspapers' readers play a vital role in its continuous publication. Their perceptions and receptions to a local paper will determine if they patronize it or not. Therefore, audience reception must be considered all the time as well.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The researcher conducted this case study to determine the changing nature of community media in a digital environment. The study unpacked the underlying issues and new concepts involving five (5) publications in the province of Cavite that experienced digital shift resulting to electronic community paper. To further investigate and provide substantive information through informants' narratives, the researcher applied a qualitative design through in-depth interview that engaged heads, or the Editors-in-Chief of the publications subjected in the conduct of the study. Relatively, each of them was given an informed consent in view of the purpose of the study and a copy of guide questions prior to the approved date of interview. After the interview, the researcher analyzed the data by means of transcribing it and used thematic analysis to formulate validated themes. The themes were in accordance with each part of the questionnaire and further discussion was successfully made in the previous chapter.

In this context, the case study in the province of Cavite shed light on the resilience and adaptation of traditional media in the face of digital change. Regardless of the size of population, the study offered information about the ecology of community media. In order to elucidate these shifts in representation, the researcher provided a comparison of the ownership, budgetary allocation, manpower, production, and distribution processes of their outlet from both the "then" and "now" perspectives.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the study concluded that:

1. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

Media Ownership

The selected publications, even after they shifted digitally, are still reliant on the municipality where it belongs, making almost all the participants involved in this study as a government-owned type of media that provides a statist approach. Also, it was concluded that if these publications support the initiatives of their local government in terms of information dissemination and other community-based reports, the online outlet will continue to operate. However, despite the reality that they considered digital adaptation, its nature as a community media and a developer of civic engagement remained the same.

Undeniably, several discourse may arise to question the intention of a community-based publication that is owned by a local government. Even though it may be up for debate, these publications largely uphold the idea that their job is to serve the interests of the community. This is evident in the news and content they post on social media about things like class suspensions, development projects, fund transparency, inflation, and conflict reports, among other things. Indeed, in the case of digital shift among selected publications as narrated by the heads, it was concluded that these entities are functioning in a digital environment for the people regardless of the type of ownership identified.

Budget Allocation

As for the budgetary allocation, the researcher concluded that a minimal difference in the financial aspect of the paper occurred. Back then, the identified publications were required to allot a budget for transportation and gathering which are both part of newspaper planning. However, when they underwent digitization, it became less expensive since their staff can work at the safety of their home particularly during pandemic.

It is also worth noting that even though they are currently using Facebook as their social media platform, majority of the informants mentioned that they still hope to strengthen their employees by involving them in a training or workshop designed to enhance their online media skills for the benefit of their paper. This strengthens the fact that these community newsletters in a digital environment are not complacent and want nothing but the best for their paper and community development.

Hence, since it was revealed that a decrease in budget is seemed advantageous due to its decreasing nature, it is still worth mentioning that despite encountered change, community-based publication still needs continuous budget allocation from several entities in the government because local patronage is not enough for them to thrive.

Manpower

It was concluded that manpower can now be seen as less challenging compared when they were only publishing traditionally since digital environment provided time and space where communication such as task designation or planning can be conducted at the comfort of their home.

Moreover, in terms of work assignment, digital environment paved way to lesser support and demands from the office where staff, writers for example, were often tasked to submit specific write ups.

In context, back when the publication was producing traditionally, most of the members of the papers including writers and layout artists were appointed by the Mayor or already working under a certain office such as Tourism Office. It was a challenge to publish an issue due to some delays seen in the output because most of the staff were not trained or did not have any formal training in journalism. At present, when they shifted digitally, it was explained in this study that one publication experienced decrease in terms of the number of staff since the office involved in budgeting did not hire additional staff, rather, they just utilized the sole skills of the head of the paper, and it brought a lot of challenges in terms of news and information gathering. It could also be perceived as stressful once the head of the paper decided to work alone and that very instance happened on one of the participants in this study.

2. The Production Process and its Changing Nature in a Digital Environment in terms of:

Content Gathering

In conclusion, content gathering has become much easier at present. As presented in this study, there was a consistent weekly meeting in the past to supervise the release of the paper but when they shifted online, news planning was no longer a constant activity. However, their manner of gathering information remained ethical, especially in sourcing materials and conducting interviews.

In terms of online gathering, all the informants said that they never failed to ensure proper crediting for their posts as well as formal logistics to keep the paper's integrity.

The aforementioned characteristics would always be significant among development communicators because practitioners must realize all the time the potential risk or if they took the job of a reporter or community journalist on the ground less seriously.

Content Packaging

In the advent of technology, the research concluded, based on the interview, that the noticeable change among the present situation of these publications is their attitude which they became extra careful in writing and laying out their electronic community media to avoid any fallacy, inaccuracy, and they even secured their paper's authenticity to prevent any illegal grabbing of content.

The researcher also highlighted the case and proved that despite its adaptation and navigation in an unfamiliar venue, majority of the participants are still practicing ethical journalism and continuously upholding its core which is to seek truth and do no harm.

Undeniably, it is a clear indication that community newspapers are significant tools that have the capacity to narrow down specific issues involving each constituent and at the same time it can magnify solutions by bringing reliable sources of information. Therefore, despite its digital look, community media in this new era are still a weapon of truth and a champion of people in the grassroots.

3. The Distribution Process and its Changing Nature in a Digital Environment in terms of:

Medium or Outlet

In conclusion, four (4) publications back then used a magazine type of paper (glossy) while the other used a short-sized bond paper. As for the observed change, all the publications have a Facebook page and two (2) of them have an existing website that is managed by their team.

In addition, when it comes to feedback mechanism, the majority of these publications based their audience's reception on the number of reactions and comments as these participants are more active on using Facebook as a medium. Relatively, while these publications are taking the effort to innovate, they may have difficulties in this digital world since one drawback of accessing online media is its constant dynamic nature, which means that users may become confused by the things it offers.

However, it is concluded that despite unfamiliarity and the statement that social media is not for everyone, when learned and managed responsibly, it can be a very useful digital space.

Frequency of Releasing

For the record, since the government owns the publication for its development projects and other significant events, in the past, the paper can be distributed monthly inside municipal hall as well as nearby offices, including elementary and high schools. Meanwhile, in this digital environment, the editorial board opted to post often when these newsletters went digital because,

given the possibilities of social media, they found it easier and faster to convey pertinent information.

However, it was concluded that even though their paper is now accessible online, there will always be difficulties. For example, individuals without internet access may find it difficult to access their content. Additionally, because their digital media is still in its infancy, they are making every effort to publicize it and help their constituents become more familiar with the page and website, an issue that is expected to happen especially for those who are trying to establish their own community-based publication or media outlet.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drawn to further support the significance of the study in accordance with the case studied:

For the **Local Government Unit (LGU)** that underwent digital transformation, it is of great help to constantly provide segmented trainings among the editorial staff that could further enhance not only the visual presence of their online media but would also equip the staff to become efficient and responsible social media managers.

Other **media organizations** may consider engaging in the community media across areas in the Philippines through dialogues and initiatives led by **development communicators** to support those who are starting to navigate the digital environment and do not have any prior knowledge yet.

Center for Community Journalism and Development, through the findings in this case study, should continue mainstreaming existing challenges

and opportunities involving community media across provinces to further identify areas of improvement and would later solidify sustainability through tangible support from other willing partners.

Lastly, **future researchers** may delve into reception analysis of digital community media among constituents such as the feedback mechanism and data analytics or tackle the quantitative aspect that would potentially bring more insights and unveiling of phenomenon regarding the characteristics of community media in this ever-changing and fast-evolving society.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter of Request

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION STUDIES

16 May 2023

MR. VERNIE CAISIP
Tourism Consultant
Municipality of Indang

Dear Mr. Caisip:

Warm and peaceful greetings,

I, Regel L. Mozol, am a graduating student from the University of the Philippines under the Master of Development Communication program. I wrote this letter to humbly ask your help in serving as one of the research participants of my study.

I am currently finishing my master thesis entitled **"The Changing Nature of Community Media: A Case Study in the Province of Cavite"**. I am analyzing and providing evidences as to how selected community newsletters/newspapers in Cavite thrived and transformed in a digital environment. This will establish the relevance of community media even in the midst of technological advancement. In order to accomplish my data gathering procedure, I need to interview existing newsletters/ newspapers in Cavite to shed light on the experiences of establishing the aforementioned medium from then and now. Relatively, I will provide you a copy of interview guide questions prior to the scheduled meeting.

I assure you that there are no known risks to participation as I like to secure that all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. This means that your answers will not be accessible, except for me and my thesis adviser.

Thank you very much for giving me your time and effort as it means a lot to me in order to graduate. I guarantee that I shall conduct the interview with respect and professionalism. May the good Lord bless you more and keep you and your family safe especially in these trying times.

Sincerely,

Regel L. Mozol
Researcher

VERNIE CAISIP
5-23-23

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
Open University

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Dear participant,

I, a graduate student under the program Master of Development Communication, would like to humbly ask for your participation in my thesis.

Relatedly, I would like to highlight in this letter that your participation is completely voluntary. You may decide whether or not to take part in this request, as long as you will inform me immediately. If you decide to participate, your signature is needed on the consent form. On the other hand, if you wish to withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your information will be disregarded.

There are no known risks to participation as I like to assure that all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. This means that your answers will not be accessible, except for me.

Consent

I have read the information (or had the information read to me) and I am aware that I am being asked to participate in an in-depth interview. I have had the opportunity to ask questions. I voluntarily agree to participate in this data gathering procedure.

ERVIN ACE H. NAVARETTE

Printed Name and Signature

JUNE 15, 2023

Date

Prepared by:

REGEL L. MOZOL
Researcher

APPENDIX B

Informed Consent

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES

Open University
Los Baños, Laguna

Date _____

Informed Consent Form for: Office of the Mayor of Indang, Cavite

Part I: Information Sheet

Warmest Greetings!

I, Regel L. Mozol, a graduate student under Master of Development Communication program at UP Open University, am currently conducting my thesis entitled ***“The Changing Nature of Community Media: A Case Study in the Province of Cavite.”***

I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable about the research.

This consent form may contain words that you do not understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain.

Purpose of the Research

In this case study, I will digest and explain the changing nature of community media in Cavite and how traditional news outlets shifted to electronics or digital counterparts. Specifically, it attempts to elucidate how a traditional medium had evolved in a digital age and how the environment was affected because of changes in the medium.

Participant Selection

You are being invited to take part in this research because I feel that your experience as a local official can contribute much to my understanding and knowledge of the topic.

Procedures

Once you are ready and have decided to take part in this interview, you will be given a questionnaire which consists of guide questions. I would like to inform you that if you do not wish to answer any of the questions during the interview, you may say so and I

will move on to the next question. No one else but me will be present unless you would like someone else to be there. The information recorded is confidential, and aside from me, no one else except **Dr. Melina F. Lumanta** (*Thesis Adviser*) will have access to the information documented during your interview. The entire interview will be audio-recorded for me to get the full and accurate information. The audio file will be kept under my protection as well as the mentioned adviser above. Moreover, I will not ask you to share personal beliefs, practices or stories and you do not have to share any knowledge that you are not comfortable sharing.

Duration

I will visit your office twice. One is to give you invitation and the other is wherein interview will be held. Expect that the interview session will only last for about an hour except if you wish to share more, and that will be highly appreciated.

Risks

If the discussion becomes very personal and confidential that you may feel uncomfortable talking about some of the topics, you do not have to answer any question or take part in the interview if you do not wish to do so. You do not have to give me any reason for not responding to any question, or for refusing to take part in the interview. Hence, if for example, the discussion is on opinions on government policies and community beliefs, and in general no personal information is sought, then the text under risks could read something like, there is a risk that you may share some personal or confidential information by chance, or that you may feel uncomfortable talking about some of the topics. I do not wish for this to happen.

Benefits

Your participation could bring a lot of benefits especially for Indang. Aside from your own municipality, the editorial staff and local officers of municipalities among provinces who also experienced a digital shift would be enlightened more and potentially find solace through your narratives in this study. Thus, it may provide more understanding on their resilience and capabilities to produce and disseminate information in the midst of technological challenges.

The development journalism perspective in this study might add new knowledge towards community development through pandemic-driven newsletters or the electronic ones as these materials can be studied and analyzed as proliferators of mobilization.

Sharing the Results

The result of the interview will be documented and read properly. It will be added to help me discuss or explain the changing nature of community media. At the end of the research, it will be shared and presented to the selected panel to give knowledge on the transformation of community media from then up to now.

Right to Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so, and choosing to participate will not affect your job or job-related evaluations in any way. You may stop participating in the interview at any time that you wish without your job being affected. I will give you an opportunity at the end of the interview to review your remarks, and you may ask to modify or remove portions of those, if you do not agree with my notes or if I did not understand you correctly.

Who to Contact

If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact me via:

Mobile Number: 0969 297 5209

Email Address: rmozol@up.edu.ph

Part II: Certificate of Consent

I have been invited to participate in the research entitled **“The Changing Nature of Community Media: A Case Study of Digital Shift Among Selected Publications in the Province of Cavite.”**

(This section is mandatory)

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked have been answered with satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

(Statement by the researcher/person taking consent)

I have accurately read the information sheet to the potential participant and made sure to the best of my ability that the participants understand it well.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this ICF has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of the Researcher taking the consent
Signature of the Researchers taking the consent _____

REGEL L. MOZOL

Date _____
Day/month/year

Attached is the set of guide questions to further explain the interview motives, as well as to assist you. Thank you and may the good Lord bless you more.

APPENDIX C

Interview Guide Questionnaire

Interview Guide Questions

Name of Publication: _____
Length of Publication: _____
Position: _____

Part I. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

A. Media Ownership

1. If you could recall, who first managed your paper and how was it back then?
2. Now that you have a digitized version, how do you secure the ownership of your paper?

B. Budget Allocation

1. How much did the local government allot for the production of your community newsletter when you were just starting?
2. How do you manage your finances back then?
3. What are your observed differences in terms of finances now that you are using internet and electronics compared when you are printing hard copies?
4. How is the management of budget at present considering the pandemic and inflation?

C. Manpower

1. How do you describe the role designation or appointment when you first started your paper?
2. How do you compare the number of staff back then now that you transitioned to digital?
3. What are the selection processes to become a part of the paper back then?
4. Is there any difference in terms of role selection in the past when compared in the present. If yes, could you please explain.

Part II. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

(Production Process)

A. Content Gathering

1. Before pandemic, how it feels like to plan for news and information gathering?
2. How do you designate the beat or piece of information back when there is no disruption in terms of physical movement?
3. How do you set up interviews before pandemic?
4. In relation, now that you are in a digital environment, how do you find your content gathering?
5. Is there any difference compared in the past? If there is, could you please explain.

B. Content Packaging

1. Before pandemic, how was your way of writing?
2. How about editing and lay-outing?
3. Is it easier now that you are in a digital environment. If yes, how do say so?
4. What do you think are the challenges now that you are in a digital environment?

Part III. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

(Distribution Process)

A. Medium or Outlet

1. How do you describe your medium or outlet back then?
2. What is a more convenient outlet for you? Please explain.
3. What is the challenge of transforming your medium and realigning it with the demands of a digital environment? Please explain.

B. Frequency of Releasing

1. How was the experience when you were still releasing your paper before pandemic?

2. How do you describe the challenges of releasing an issue back then?
3. Now that you have shifted digitally, what are the things you have observed when disseminating information to your community?
4. What do you think are the advantages of releasing an issue in a digital environment?
5. How about disadvantages at present?

APPENDIX D

Coding Sheet

General Problem:

How is community media transforming within the digital environment?

Sample:

QUESTION	INTERVIEW EXTRACT	CODE	THEME
<p>Part I. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:</p> <p>A. Media Ownership</p> <p><i>If you could recall, who first managed your paper and how was it back then?</i></p>			

APPENDIX D

Interview Transcription

Date of Interview: 16 May 2023

Interviewee: Mr. Vernie Caisip

Name of Printed Publication: Balitang Indang

Position: Tourism Consultant, Municipality of Indang

Interviewer: So, sir 'yung ngayon po... 'yung pangalan po ng dyaryo ninyo ay...

Interviewee: 'Yun 'yung Balitang Indang. Pero unfortunately, naka-stop na 'yung publication niya as of now. So, wala kami. 'Yun nga 'yung first and last na lumabas 'yun e.

Interviewer: 'Yun po 'yung printed po?

Interviewee: Oo, 'yun 'yung printed na dinistribute namin na nakailang... ewan ko e, 1,000 copies din naman 'yun na na-circulate.

Interviewer: Madami rin po.

Interviewee: Oo, after no'n, 'yun nga 'yung nagiging problema ko. Dapat kasi 'yon, parang semi-annual e. Dalawang beses sa isang taon namin nilalabas. Unfortunately, 'yung team na dinelegate ko for that, nu'ng second part na, hindi na nakapag-contribute ng articles so, 'yun 'yung, alangan na, natambakan na rin kami ng trabaho, alangan naman na ako ulit gumawa no'n lahat.

Interviewer: So, from 2016, sir... nag-end po siya ng?

Interviewee: Ng 2017. Kasi lumabas 'yung 2016 namin, parang latter part ng 2016. Tapos pagpasok ng 2017 dapat 'yung first sa... initial for 2017, hindi na lumabas.

Interviewer: Okay po.

Interviewee: Ta's kasi ang naging ano ro'n kasi do'n kaya hindi na rin naming kinonsider... napunta lahat sa social media saka sa website.

Interviewer: Ah, so parang nagkaroon po kayo ng digital version.

Interviewee: Oo, doon na siya.

Interviewer: Kailan po nag-start 'yun, sir?

Interviewee: Ano rin e, halos magkasunod din sila. Parang nu'ng ni-release 'yung publication na printed, the end of 2016, in-activate na rin 'yung social media account tapos 'yung website pinaayos ko na rin by 2017. So, ang nangyayari sa kanya, naging synchronized kasi 'yon e. Once nag-post ka sa Facebook, official page ng municipality, automatic 'yon nagre-reflect sa website. 'Yung official website ng Indang. So, hindi na namin nakita 'yung need for the revival of the printed version.

Interviewer: Ah okay.

Interviewee: Saka mas mabilis e. Mabilis 'yung turn out. Kapag sa article sa Facebook ka gumawa, kumbaga fresh na fresh 'yung news. Unlike kapag printed kasi, ang mangyayari magazine version lang siya e. Pipili ka lang ng isang article, magfo-focus ka do'n tapos after no'n, saka bago mo sya ma-publish... months. So, 'yung article mo parang ano nga magazine article.

Interviewer: Same lang, sir ng pangalan 'yung nasa social media? Same lang po ng title?

Interviewee: Hindi, naging ano na 'yung nasa social media e... naging Official Facebook Page na siya. Hindi na siya "Balitang Indang". Tapos 'yung lumalabas sa, meron din do'ng regarding sa History, regarding sa ano, kung

ano naging ano na lang siya, random na 'yung pagpo-post ng articles. Unlike sa printed version, nakaayos talaga siya.

Interviewer: Sir, punta po tayo noon sa printed po, gaano po kalaki ang ina-allot niyo po for the printed po? Kapag nagri-release po kayo?

Interviewee: No'n kasi, 'di ko matandaan kung magkano lumabas per page... parang 11 pesos per page. Kasi ano sya, 'yung paper nya hindi 'yung newspaper type. 'Yung glossy. Ang ginamit naming no'n is 'yung C2S na Wanted pa yata. Basta 'yung pang-page ng magazine.

Interviewer: Ah, maliit lang po talaga?

Interviewee: Hindi, I mean 'yung type ng paper, 'yung glossy na coated tapos back-to-back 'yon pero isang page lang sya na malaki e na size ng newspaper pero kapag hinawakan mo sya glossy sya. Para syang magazine. So, 'yun 'yung nagpamahal sa kanya. Unlike 'yung newspaper talaga na manipis... quality lang 'yung sa'min, parang magazine, meron kaming isang page na Malaki na parang magazine type.

Interviewer: Sir, sino po ang nagma-manage noon?

Interviewee: Accounting pa rin. Pero may budget kasi kami for PIO namin, 'yung Public Information Officer, under din ng Office of the Mayor. So, doon, meron kaming allotted budget para sa ganyan na kinukuhanan namin.

Interviewer: Paano sa social media, sir... nagba-budget din ba kayo?

Interviewee: Hindi, itong sa social media, wala rin naman tayo... kumbaga free naman siya. 'Yung website, 'yung official website kasi binabayaran namin 'yung domain, 'yung hosting. So, ayun 'yung mga technical aspect na kailangan mong

bayaran. Nababayaran naman namin sya. Subscription kumbaga. Kasi kailangan mo 'yung domain no'n na binibili mo, 'yung www.Indang.ph. Although meron ng government na libre, hindi sya gano'n kaano kaya meron kaming subscription na sarili kasi mas efficient 'yon.

Interviewer: Hanggang ngayon, sir?

Interviewee: Oo, kaya kapag chineck mo sya, 'yung website, although ngayon pina-revise ko ulit, pero existing sya kapag chineck mo. Makikita 'yon sa Facebook e, 'di ba meron do'n kapag clinick mo.

Interviewer: Sir, sa manpower po ano 'yung pinagkaiba noong nagpi-print pa kayo tapos ngayon po? Nabawasan po ba or same?

Interviewee: Oo, kasi 'yun nga ang naging challenge kaya hindi na siya na-revive, 'yung printed version. Kasi do'n mo mari-realize na talagang kailangan mo ng isang entity sa ganitong institution na parang media. Meron ka rin talaga for PR saka na media dapat na team. Kasi ang nangyari no'n kumuha lang ako per department ng contributors... ng mga empleyado. So, from agriculture kukuha ka ng isa. Tapos from sa anong department, kung sino man na ano, kukuha ka lang. Tapos sila 'yung pag-iisipin mo, e hindi naman talaga sila nakatutok do'n. Parang ano lang 'yon e, parang side work nila. Ang focus pa rin nila ay 'yung task talaga nila. Actually, hindi nila nagagawa kasi hindi talaga sila para do'n. Unlike kapag meron kang team na media talaga, 'yun lang, kumbaga naka-focus ka na mag-isip ng article. Kaya minsan, 'yung pangalawang publication sana naming, nakita mo, binigay nila na info sa akin for the next article medyo malayo na sa... kumbaga hindi gano'n kaganda 'yung lumabas na mga article. Kasi pinipilit na lang e.

Interviewer: Oh, okay po.

Interviewee: So, 'yun 'yung isang challenge na kung magre-recommend ka sa mga ganitong institution, talagang media, I mean meron talagang entity, kung hindi man department na group na naka ano lang, focus do'n sa task.

Interviewer: Sa tingin nyo, sir ano po ang mas mahirap sa pagpili po ng staff... noon o ngayon, sir na nasa social media na kayo?

Interviewee: 'Yung sa social media ang gumagawa lang ako... ako lang ang nag-a approve. Minsan ako na rin ang naggagawa ng write up. Tapos may isa akong staff na gano'n din, minsan papa-check nya sa'kin, sya 'yung gagawa ng write up... mabilis.

Interviewer: Pa'nong mabilis, sir?

Interviewee: Mabilis kasi 'pag... halimbawa kagaya no'n may event si Mayor na pinuntahan so, kasama nya kami. Minsan pasasamahin ko 'yung magpi-picture. Minsan nga kahit 'yung security lang ni Mayor na closed-in, 'pag ka mabilisan pini-picturan si Mayor, sini-send sa akin. Ayon, tapos gagawan lang namin ng info kung ano 'yung event na pinuntahan nya. Tapos ayon, po-post mo na agad sya. Tapos ang masarap sa... ang kagandahan talaga ng social media is anytime pwede mo i-edit. 'Pag meron kang na-miss out na detail, pwede mo ipasok anytime. Unlike 'pag nag-print kana, kailangan 'yung proofreading no'n... basta na-print mo, wala na 'yon. So, 'yun 'yung disadvantage talaga. Tapos may cost ka pa sa printing. Unlike sa social media, wala.

Interviewer: Sir, pagdating sa, punta po tayo sa pagga-gather po, pagpili po ng mga ilalagay ninyo sa dyaryo, sir ano 'yung planning stage niyo po compared noon... saka ngayon?

Interviewee: Noon kasi, usually, may regular meeting kami noon. Nagpapatawag ako ng meeting tapos parang ginawan ko sya ng organizational chart. Kumbaga direction, naka-flow chart 'yung articles, 'yung pinaka-structure ng newsletter. So, meron kaming main feature, ito 'yung tungkol sa mandate ni Mayor, 'yung ginagawa nya tapos meron kang mga articles do'n na naka-focus sa history, sa environment, sa tourism, culture... so, nakagano'n lang sya. Madali. Kumbaga andu'n na 'yung pinakaano mo, du'n ka lang mag-iisip kung ano'ng ipapasok mong articles.

Interviewer: Paano po kayo nagde-designate, sir... sino pong gagawa nito... sa culture...

Interviewee: Usually, du'n sa department na concern. 'Pag culture, ang ano niyan... tourism. Tapos depende kung meron kaming resource person coming from another department. Halimbawa meron dito do'n sa assessor, nu'ng nabubuhay pa 'yung dating boss naming, si Sir Chito... so, marami syang connection, marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling 'yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.

Interviewer: Hanggang ngayon, sir... sa social media ganyan pa rin po 'yung planning nyo po? 'Yung planning stage nyo po?

Interviewee: Oo, meron pa rin kaming gano'n. Usually gano'n 'yung tina-tap namin. Actually, ngayon mas lumaki kasi minsan meron kaming mga articles or

kagaya ng Bonifacio Day... 'yung celebration ng Bonifacio Day. Meron kaming sarili pero minsan kumukuha kami ng info from National Government— Philippine Information Agency. Usually, gano'n ang ginawa ko nu'ng ano e, na parang 'pag ka ang event o ang information ay means of national concern, usually ang source mo ay 'yung mga government agencies na concerned. Number 1 'yung PIA, Public Information Agency ng Malacanang. Tapos ang Malacanang may sarili ring ano e press... so, usually doon kami nag-aano. Pagdating naman sa DOST, number 1 do'n lalo 'pag ang ipa-publish mo ay national concern... bagyo, 'yung mga... lalo na 'yung COVID... nu'ng time ng COVID nag-iba rin ang... sobrang naging critical ng public information namin na... dissemination namin. Kasi sobrang ano, critical na lahat ng ilalabas mo, inaanatay ng tao. 'Yun 'yung actually time din na nag-iba din talaga lalo 'yung form nu'ng communication namin. 'Yung pagdi-disseminate namin ng information publicly. So, from newsletter... social media... parang means of ano lang e PR lang talaga sya. Ipapakita mo lang 'yung ginagawa ng munisipyo saka programs. Pero nu'ng time ng COVID, talagang ano na sya, naging ano na sya, nag-shift sya sa talagang information. Na kailangan 'yung information na ilalabas mo, sobrang accurate, sobrang talagang nire-review nyo, sobrang technical. So, 'yun 'yung naging transformation nya. Na mabuti, nakapag-start kami ng newsletter, parang nagkaroon kami ng means nga ng pag-ano... pag-disseminate kasi at least nu'ng dumating 'yung COVID, hindi bago sa'min e. Kumbaga parang nasimulan na naming ta's hanggang ngayon pati 'yung pagre-report ng COVID, ng cases, tapos lahat ng dumadating na protocol, ako kasi 'yung naging in-charge ng overall operation ng COVID response ng lahat ng munisipyo... sa'kin in-assign ni Mayor. Parang overall coordinator saka in-

charge of operations. So, lahat ng information dumadaan muna sa akin. Galing DOH, galing ano, galing IATF. So, 'pag dumating sa'min 'yung information 'yung sa task force, sa IATF, after mo mabasa kasi Word lang naman 'yun e, 'yung lumalabas, ang problema mo ngayon pa'no mo ire-relay sa mga taga-Indang... sa local. Sa locality. So, ayon, gumagawa kami ng mga visual ano, makikita mo 'yung mga "Confirmed Case", 'yung mga gano'n gano'n, suspected case, tapos kailangan mo gumawa ng mga infographics para mabilis. Kung hindi man picture, infographics, para lang maintindihan ng mga tao. Mabigat. Pinaka naging challenging 'yung time ng COVID.

Interviewer: Sir, nag-i interview rin kayo noon po tapos ngayon po?

Interviewee: Meron kami, 'yung pinaka-interview na kinonduct is during newsletter time. 'Yung printed. Kasi do'n nga, ang nangyari sa kanya ay para syang magazine type e. Kagaya no'n, 'yung pinakamatandang magkakalamay sa Indang ininterview. So, pati 'yon naghanap sila ng mga resource person do'n na magbibigay ng story tungkol sa ano ng kalamay. 'Yung mga gano'n, 'yun 'yung kaibahan sa social media. Sa Facebook naman, sa social media, mabilis kaya lang hindi sya... sa newsletter mas pinag-iisipan mo. Meron talagang planning. Unlike social media, para syang 'yung news talaga na on-the-go ka e kung ano'ng nangyayari. Kailangan sumabay ka. So, magkaiba sila ng discipline kumbaga. So, 'yun 'yung ano natin do'n.

Interviewer: Sir, sa ano naman tayo sa write up po. Before pandemic sir ano po 'yung napansin ninyong kaibahan nu'ng nagsusulat kayo noon tapos ngayon po... sa social media na kayo? May pinagkaiba po ba? Mas nahirapan po ba kayo sa editing, sa sulat po?

Interviewee: Ang pagsusulat nu'ng time ng newsletter... ng printed nga... ah ano sya, kumbaga manggagaling ang mga articles sa mga tao. Sa mga tao, 'yung mga nagsusulat talaga. Tapos 'yon babasahin mo. Then, afterwards re-review-hin mo pa, ipu-proofread mo pa... 'yung mga gano'n. Unlike dito sa social media ako na lang gagawa. Usually pa, Tagalog. Para kasi ano, kailangan iisipin mo 'yun 'yung inaano ng tao. 'Yun naming newsletter naming dalawang version... Tagalog saka English. Parang 'yung paragraph no'n, meron syang English... may dalawa sya. So, 'yun 'yung ano no'n. 'Yung 'yung kaibahan lang nya. So, kumbaga pinaplano mo ngayon sa newsletter, itong sa social media impromptu.

Interviewer: Pero may na-encounter po kayong challenges, sir? Sa pagsulat sa social media?

Interviewee: Madami rin kasi... minsan 'yung pagko-construct mo ng paragraphs. Minsan paulit-ulit e. Kasi nasasanay kana nga. Minsan 'yung pinagawa ko, 'yung staff. Kina-copy paste nya from last year e. 'Yung info. Sabi ko kasi para mabilis gano'n tapos ine-edit ko na lang. 'Yun sya usually. Ang magiging ano mo... social media... may tendency ka na parang iisa lang 'yung magiging flow ng ano mo... kasi sanay kana e. Kumbaga usual alam mo na 'pag si Mayor umikot, 'pag may mga event... parang paulit-ulit lang naman. Unlike sa newsletter nga talagang pinag-iisipan.

Interviewer: Sir, puwede mo bang i-share kung ano 'yung pinagdaanan niyong hirap no'ng papunta pa lang kayo sa social media?

Interviewee: 'Yon nga... number one is ito 'yung institution mo, hindi naman sya... hindi sila exposed du'n sa media unlike ako... galing ako sa advertising,

sa media talaga. Sa private. Dito, ang hirap mong iano... although alam nila na dapat may gano'n... merong pailan-ilan na tao na dapat alam nila na sa publication, meron kang... pero hindi lahat well-versed pagdating sa gano'n. Para kang nagsisimula sa scratch e. Tuturuan mo pa sila. Tapos sasabihin magbasa muna kayo nito. Hindi nila nature 'yung... 'pag hindi ka galing sa industry nga ng may journ, pagdating sa kanila... mababaguhan ka talaga. Hindi nila ginagawa... hindi nila gagawin kung hindi mo o-orderan. Saka 'yung creativity in terms of writing, ibang iba 'yung sa inyo... 'yung nasa media... nasa academe. Pagdating dito sa mga ganito.

Interviewer: Ano po, sir napansin nyo po dito?

Interviewee: Kumbaga ano, hindi sila... 'yun nga number one hindi gano'n ka-sharpen 'yung creativity. So, kumbaga parang sila, kung ano lang 'yung info, as is. Pero hindi nila ire-relay na parang storytelling. 'Yun nga medyo mababa 'yung creativity na hindi mo naman pwede paghanapan sila kasi sasabihin nila, "Hindi naman namin trabaho 'yan." So, 'yun 'yung mga aspect na 'pag galing ka sa ano tapos gusto mong magkaro'n ng... mag-materialize 'yung concept na ginagamit mo sa ibang industry na ilalagay mo rito, so, pipigain mo talaga sila. Mahihirapan ka. So, maraming trabaho on your part. Kumbaga sa'kin o kung dalawa lang kaming nakakaintindi halos kami lahat 'yung umaayos. So, kumbaga 'yung makukuha mo lang sa kanila ay piling pili lang. Eventually naman naiintindihan nila kaya lang iba pa rin 'yung may mga tao ka na aral saka trained for that. So, 'yun 'yung kaibahan.

Interviewer: Sir, nasa dulong part na po tayo. Sir, 'yung sa pagre-release po noon sa printed... ano po 'yung challenges ninyo noon saka ngayon na nasa social media na kayo? 'Yung pagre-release po ng paper.

Interviewee: 'Yung sa release naman no'n since 'yun lang naman ang talaga ang advantage ng nasa local government ka or nasa government entity ka, 'yung manpower mo saka 'yung resources mo ay hindi sya magiging... unlike sa private... once na nag-publish ka or nag-release ka... merong cost. Syempre mag-aano ka pa rin naman... kung paano ka magre-release, kung paano mo sya ide-deploy kumbaga 'yung materials mo. Ito, hinde, isang patawag mo lang ng meeting, patawag mo 'yung mga Kapitan, bigyan mo ng tag-isang kopya tapos... kasi regular naman meeting namin e. So, anytime... kaya nga dito 'yun 'yung kagandahan e. Lahat ng resources mo, anytime, isang tawag mo lang wala kang problema. 'Yung pag-produce mo lang talaga coming from your side lalo na kung pa'no mo gagawin 'yung materials. 'Yun 'yung challenge pero 'yung pag-dispose mo, pag-disseminate mo physically ng mga materials napakadali. Napakadali. Wala kang problema. Wala pating cost. 'Yun na 'yung isa... walang cost kasi nga na sa'yo na lahat e.

Interviewer: Sa social media, sir... may napansin ba kayong challenges 'pagdating sa paano nyo isisigurado na nababasa ng mga tao...

Interviewee: Social media madali. Ayun 'yung napansin ko when it comes to... 'yung mga government institution lalo na 'yung may kailangan... usually kasi ikaw na hinahanap e. May kailangan sa'yo ang tao e. 'Yung information coming from you sobrang importante. Kaya nga du'n pumapasok 'yung ethics saka responsibility sobrang bigat din when it comes to institutions like this. Hindi

kagaya sya ng private na... halimbawa meron kang blog or social media page na private... kailangan mong mag-attract ng viewers, ng followers. Ikaw kukuha ng audience. Unlike itong sa amin kami ang inaantay ng tao na maglabas kasi automatic 'yan meron e... maglabas ka lang... alam mo naman 'yan laging trending e kahit nu'ng nag-talk ako sa CAS, trending lagi 'yung walang pasok. Sabi ko nga ako 3 AM gising na kami ni Mayor. Nagtatawagan na kami nyan kasi masama ang panahon. Kasi as early as 5 AM kailangan may naka-post. Bago pa mag-post si Mayor, nagtatawagan na kami nya. Nag-post na ba si Gov? Nakabantay ako sa laptop. Tapos sa cellphone. Tapos sa TV. Kung ano'ng mga mangyayari? Kasi dalawa lang kaming gising e. Ako lang 'yung magpo-post e. Wala kaming... 'yung mga staff namin ano na...

Interviewer: Pati designing, sir?

Interviewee: Oo, ako na rin. Kasi nga 'yun 'yung trabaho ko e. Nag-art director ako... creative director ako ng agency... creative agency. Mostly talaga, sa design talaga ang trabaho ko. Sa creative. 'Yun 'yung ginagamit ko. Kaya minsan talaga, kahit nu'ng time ng COVID, 'yun na 'yung... wala akong maasahan e. 'Yan 'yang mga 'yan, 'yang mga *Indang Atin 'To* na mga yan... ako gumagawa nyan. Kasi nga wala ka ditong makukuhang tao. Na 'yung sa discipline mo or galing sa industry mo na meron dito. Mahirap. Bihira. So, talagang tyatyagain mo sya. 'Yun 'yung challenge ng pagdya-dyaryo. Unless maggawa ka talaga. Mag-recruit ka ng tao for that purpose alone. 'Yun lang. Kasi sino ba tatanggap dito? Magkano lang ang JO dito... 360 a day... tapos kukuha ng creative person na kayang sumweldo sa Manila or online ng medyo okay na hindi umaalis ng bahay. So, medyo challenging.

Interviewer: Sir, ano 'yung parang pinaka-drive nyo, sir bakit kayo nagpapatuloy?

Interviewee: Una kasi, kaya lang din ako kinuha ni Mayor na consultant, PR at sa Tourism kasi nga nu'ng prinopose ko sa kanila 'yung mga 'yan... pa'no ka magre-relay ng mga information creatively saka 'yung mga campaign. So kumbaga... kasi kailangan ng tao atsaka mas madaling maiintindihan... kumbaga 'yung public service na binibigay nila nandu'n 'yung missing link usually... dati ha, dati... ngayon kasi hindi na kasi 'yung mga national government meron nang mga creative... meron na. Dati kasi 'yung missing link is because how you would communicate with the people creatively. Kasi 'pag information lang... usually, mga dumadating naman sa'min mga papel e. Mga memo. So, pa'no mo sya iko-convey sa tao na maiintindihan nila? So, usually do'n pumapasok ang "mass comm..." ...communication. So, 'yung how you interpret 'yung mga information para 'yung tao, it's either maintindihan nila creatively or mas madali mong ma-relay sa kanila 'yung information na hindi sila maguguluhan. So, 'yun 'yung isa sa mga drive ko tapos 'yun nga parang 'yung discipline sa creative agency... advertising... magagamit sobra ng mga government institutions, 'yun 'yung iniisip ko dati na totoo naman talaga nagagamit. So, 'yun 'yung drive na parang... kumbaga sa'kin experimental e. So, 'yun 'yung naging ano. Tapos 'yun nga tumagal kasi kaya nu'ng tumagal na ko nang tumagal nag-iba na 'yung role ko. From consultant lang ako ng Tourism Office hanggang du'n sa naging in-charge na... para na 'kong naging admin. Administrator na 'yung nangyari. Hindi na 'ko sobrang busy. Lahat ng aspect ngayon... hindi naman sa ano... ng sa munisipyo, parang function ni Mayor... nabibigyan ako ng ibang function nya, nahahati. Parang naging administrator

ang kinalabasan ko. Rather than du'n sa original ko na hawak ko lang ay creatives, communication, PR... ngayon medyo nag-iba na. So, 'yung drive nga is 'yun nga 'yung konting alam mo na na knowledge na natutuhan mo sa ibang industry tapos nakikita mo na parang baka mag-work dito... mas maganda tapos parang naiintindihan ng mga tao... 'yun lang naman.

Interviewer: Thank you, sir. Sobrang nasagot nyo lahat. Sobrang lalim, sir.

Date of Interview: 30 June 2023

Interviewee: Mr. Dindo T. Diago

Name of Printed Publication: Samyo

Position: Former Officer-in-Charge

Interviewer: The first question regarding sa community newspaper nyo, magkano po ang estimated budget ninyo noon sa pagpa-publish ng newspaper?

Interviewee: Since nagre-release kame annually ang budget for 5000 copies is 300,000.00.

Interviewer: Aside from local budget, may iba pa po ba kayong source na pagkukuhanan ng budget?

Interviewee: Wala. Local budget lang talaga ng munisipyo.

Interviewer: What are the factors that the municipality considered in establishing a newspaper?

Interviewee: Factors... Hmm para sa mga citizen, para malaman nila ang accomplishments ng munisipyo.

Interviewer: Ah, so bali po yung newspaper ninyo ay nagsi-circulate sa accomplishment ng munisipyo?

Interviewee: Yes. Ang nagko-contribute ay yung mga iba't-ibang departments ng munisipyo, 'yung naa-accomplish nila, pinapasa nila dito tapos kame na nag aayos... nag iintact. Dito na din nagle-lay out. The simplest explanation for this is annual accomplishment ng munisipyo na ginawang magazine type.

Interviewer: Pero nagsi-circulate po sya sa buong Carmona noon?

Interviewee: Yes. Namimigay kame sa mga barangays at schools, syempre for free 'yun.

Interviewer: May mga na-encounter po ba kayo na difficulties sa page-establish ng newspaper noon?

Interviewee: 'Yung laging problema is, minsan hindi nabibigay agad 'yung report ng bawat departments kaya nade-delay ang printing.

Interviewer: Uhm... Ano po yung nag motivate sa inyo para magtayo ng sariling newspaper?

Interviewee: Si Mayor mismo, kase gusto nya may malaman o maging updated ang mga tao sa Carmona sa mga nakamit o nagawa ng munisipyo under her term.

Interviewer: How did the newspaper get its name?

Interviewee: Ah, kase ang pangalan ng Mayor namin is Dahlia which is a flower. And ang bulaklak ay mabango. So imbes na halimuyak, Samyo na lang... somehow, it's unique.

Interviewer: Yung editorial staffs po? May mga qualifications din po ba?

Interviewee: Sa mga departments kasi may isa sa kanilang tinatawag na "Liason Officer". Sila 'yung naka-assign magsulat ng accomplishment report ng department nila.

Interviewer: Does the municipality have its own printing press po?

Interviewee: Nope. Sa isang private printing press kame. 'Yung nagle-lay out kami na din, we have an artist kasi.

Interviewer: Pa'no po nagsi-circulate noon ang newspaper nyo? Pano nakakakuha ang tao ng kopya?

Interviewee: Usually dito sa Munisipyo. Pero namimigay din kame sa schools at barangays. Sa buong Carmona talaga sya.

Interviewer: How frequent is the release or publication of community newspaper?

Interviewee: Annually.

Date of Interview: 12 June 2023

Interviewee: Mr. Ervin Ace H. Navarette

Name of Printed Publication: Banaag, Official Newsletter Publication of the City of Imus

Position: Editor-in-Chief

Part I. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

A. Media Ownership

Interviewer: Sir, salamat po sa time ninyo and sorry po sa abala. For the first question po based sa interview guide, if you could still recall, who first managed your paper, and how was it back then?

Interviewee: Si Mr. Eli Taparan 'yung unang humawak nitong newsletter dito sa Imus. Nagsimula talaga kami sa scratch... 'yung printed media namin. Inalam namin kung paano magiging effective saka pa'no mae-engage 'yung Imuseños sa pagbabasa ng news. Saka ano... kung pa'no ma-desseminate 'yung newsletters nang maayos.

Interviewer: Now that you have a digitized version, how do you secure the ownership of your paper?

Interviewee: 'Pag government kasi dapat 'yung mga newsletter nila available any time sa may gusto. Tapos para ma-secure namin 'yung papel, we make sure na it is released only through the official sites and pages ng Imus... tapos dapat may proper branding and included din dapat 'yung names ng employees na involved sa paggawa.

B. Budget Allocation

Interviewer: How much did the local government allow for the production of your community newsletter when you were starting?

Interviewee: *No comment

Interviewer: How do you manage your finances back then?

Interviewee: Ah sa finances, lahat naman ng local government talagang tsini-check nila saka nire-review yearly 'yung para sa disbursement the following year. Talagang strict saka meticulous 'yung pagba-budget. As one of the duties of the City Information Office, we must allot a budget for the City paper and produced monthly issues... regardless kung may maka-receive kami ng budget cut or not.

Interviewer: What are your observed differences in finances now that you are using the internet and electronics compared to when you are printing hard copies?

Interviewee: Sa ngayon... du'n sa digitized version ng newsletter namin, it made it easier to comply with the required papers for budget preparation. Kaso, we are still producing the same number of printed copies as before, considering the budget allocation that we receive annually. We also usually have more copies during the first half of the year.

Interviewer: How is the budget management at present, considering the pandemic and inflation?

Interviewee: Actually, 'yung Administration and the Budget Office... they value effective and accurate information dissemination tapos tinitingnan din naman

nila na essential 'yung newsletter sa public. So, the City Information Office still receives a considerable budget to accomplish its deliverables for the people.

C. Manpower

Interviewer: How do you describe the role designation or appointment when you first started your paper?

Transitioning from Congress to the Local Government Unit and being appointed as the Acting City Information Officer was a pressure and a challenge, but, at the same time, a learning experience for me to grow as an individual while serving my City.

Interviewer: How do you compare the number of staff back then now that you transitioned to digital?

Interviewee: Digitizing and, at the same time, transitioning required additional staff for the City Information Office. Idagdag mo pa na when hiring, it requires more people to help with the proper designation of tasks and efficient work delivery.

Interviewer: What are the selection processes to become a part of the paper?

Interviewee: It is the decision of the City Information Officer and the head writer to choose the people who will be part of the paper. Usually, they select newsletter staff within the City Information Office or hire additional employees.

Interviewer: Is there any difference in terms of role selection in the past when compared to the present? If yes, could you please explain?

Interviewee: Syempre oo. There is a more apparent designation of tasks based on the employees' capabilities, experience, and qualifications compared nu'ng nagsisimula pa lang kami..

Part II. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

(Production Process)

A. Content Gathering

Interviewer: Before the pandemic, how it feels to plan for news and information gathering?

Interviewee: Ay bago mag-pandemic, the approach to news and information gathering was inclined to a face-to-face approach... dagdag mo pa na hindi kami takot... we don't worry about physical distance or getting sick because of the possible exposure to the virus.

Interviewer: How do you designate the beat or piece of information back when there is no disruption in terms of physical movement?

Interviewee: *No comment

Interviewer: How do you set up interviews before the pandemic?

Interviewee: We usually set up an interview by sending a request letter or a memo to the office or employees involved with the program or project.

Interviewer: In relation, now that you are in a digital environment, how do you find your content gathering?

Interviewee: As before, we connect with different offices... tapos 'yung mga researchers namin, they verify muna the contents they gathered before giving the details to the writer saka pa nila ipo-post or print for public consumption.

Interviewer: Is there any difference compared to the past? If there is, could you please explain?

Interviewee: None. Wala naman. The functions of the City Information Office remain the same as before. Nagdo-document pa rin kami saka cover... halos same pa rin kasi we are still gathering information, researching, editing, posting, and disseminating information on current events, programs, news, and announcements. Lahat 'yon for the benefit of the public.

B. Content Packaging

Interviewer: Before the pandemic, how was your way of writing?

Interviewee: There's no particular difference in news writing pre and post-pandemic.

Interviewer: How about editing and layouts?

Interviewee: The writing, editing, and layout of the newsletter remain the same since we have staff naman na assigned to carry out their roles.

Interviewer: Is it easier now that you are in a digital environment? If yes, how do you say so?

Interviewee: It is easier in terms of communication, the processing of online requests, contacting the requesting party, and fact-checking details for accurate information dissemination.

Interviewer: What are your challenges now in a digital environment?

Interviewee: Sa challenge, siguro kapag hindi satisfied 'yung readers namin tapos mga taga-Imus pa talaga sila. Since, our task is to deliver information to the public katulad ng programs, projects, and updates sa local government ng Imus, ginagawa talaga namin 'yung best namin para ma-fact-check saka ma-verify bawat details na nari-receive namin.

Part III. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

(Distribution Process)

A. Medium or Outlet

Interviewer: How do you describe your medium or outlet back then?

Interviewee: We have produced print and digital copies of the newsletter before the pandemic. Hanggang ngayon kasi meron pa rin kami.

Interviewer: What is a more convenient outlet for you? Please explain.

Interviewee: Of course, digital is more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce e. However, we still encourage the public to read the paper through the physical document given to them; thus, we display these in every office as much as possible.

Interviewer: What is the challenge of transforming your medium and realigning it with the demands of a digital environment? Please explain.

Interviewee: One of the challenges we sometimes face is that social media users tend not to read the whole caption or context of the post, resulting in

misconception and misunderstanding that could potentially cause the further proliferation of fake news. Another challenge siguro... na we usually encounter is photo grabbers using the published materials of the City without giving proper credit.

B. Frequency of Releasing

Interviewer: How was the experience when you released your paper before the pandemic?

Interviewee: Releasing and disseminating the printed newsletter monthly in every office... outside and or extension offices... and public schools... fulfilling sya actually because we could physically see the fruit of our hard work.

Interviewer: How do you describe the challenges of releasing an issue back then?

Interviewee: One of the challenges of releasing an issue back then was the delay in printing. Also, events dated during the last week of the month would require some time for writers, editors, and proofreaders to produce articulated articles. May times na nae-experience pa rin namin pero mas better na ngayon kasi digital media na.

Interviewer: Now that you have shifted digitally, what have you observed when disseminating information to your community?

Interviewee: Information spreads in a blink, and sometimes people quickly comment without understanding the full context. 'Yun 'yung mahirap sa part ng digital.

Interviewer: What are the advantages of releasing an issue in a digital environment?

Interviewee: Information dissemination has become easier and more accessible, especially for those who have constant access to the Internet.

Interviewer: How about disadvantages at present?

Interviewee: Not every Imuseño has the capability and time to check the official outlets of the City.

Interviewer: Sir... maraming maraming salamat po.

Interviewee: Glad to help.

Date of Interview:

Interviewee: Director Rodrigo Vicencio Jr.

Name of Printed Publication: Arengkadang Silang

Position: Former Editor/ Publisher

Interviewee: Ang costing nyan, depende sa number of copies. Habang dumadami, lumalaki presyo. Pero 'dun sa first thousand, 'pag sa imprenta ka pupunta, 'yung first one thousand bibigyan ka nila kagad ng rate. Ang gastos kagad 'yung running.

Okay, ito talaga ang mga gastos, una 'yung pre-press, 'yung pagga-gather ng information, you'll use gasoline... mag-i-interview ka, mama-masahe ka. Pagkuha ng litrato, 'di kamukha nung araw, ngayon digital na. . . papa-print mo nalang. 'Yun ang initial costing, 'yun ang pre-press.

'Nung araw, type talaga, tapos dadalhin mo sa printing. . . ngayon may computer na, may spell check pa. Maliban nalang kung Tagalog. Ang community paper should be Tagalog. Lalo na't Cavite. 'Wag kayong maglalagay ng Ingles, pwede mag-taglish... wala masyadong nagbabasa ng Ingles.

Interviewer: Dominant po talaga, Tagalog?

Interviewee: Yes, tagalog region tayo eh. Ngayon, may mga sitwasyones. . . anong gusto nyo ba? Pag ka community paper, puro magaganda, pagka 'yung Tabloid style naman, may investigative reporting, pero pag ka community newspaper... puro magagandang balita ng komunidad. 'Di kamukha ng mga newspaper dito sa Cavite, merong mga binibira. 'Yung dyaryo ko dito eh... community newspaper na walang pangit na balita. Kasi aral ako kay Marcos... 'yung developmental information. Before Martial Law reporter na ako ng The Manila Times, 'nung mag-martial law, syempre susunod ka, puro magandang

balita lang. 'Nung gumawa ako ng dyaryo nung araw, 45,000 copies, lahat ng household meron.

Interviewer: Pero dito po, magkano po usually 'yung ina-allot?

Interviewee: Una, ang style ko, hindi ako pumupunta sa imprenta, eto ang gagawin ko... jabber style, kunwari ako ang naghahanap buhay, printer lang sila. So, ako, ang dadalhin ko sa kanila... camera ready. Nagawa na nung mga staffs ko 'yung istorya, andun na litrato naka-USB, ibabato nila sa plate maker sa Maynila. Pagdala nila sa Maynila, 350 per plate lamang, 4 pages. Pag ka nag-eight pages, 700. Ngayon, etong gimmick, 'yung transportation... edi ibabato nila by internet, pero 'yung plato o plantsa ipapadala dito, babayaran ko ng 250 'yon. Isasakay sa bus, ibaba roon sa imprenta. Two fifty plus two fifty... ngayon may running, sa first 1,000 no'n 350, succeeding 1,000, 250 nalang,

Interviewer: Three fifty po per page?

Interviewee: Four pages na 'yon. Ang dyaryo, maliit lamang.

Interviewer: So, magkano po ang nauubos ninyo?

Interviewee: Tama ang tanong mo. Dati pinabibili ko ang munisipyo ng papel, dadalhin ko nalang don... para makamura. Kasi 'pag imprenta ang bumili, mangangapital sila eh. Halimbawa, bili nila 5,000, binayaran nila ng 5,000 syempre 'yung pera nilang natulog for about 2 weeks, kailangan nilang kumita 'non. Pumapatak minsan ng... ang isang 4 pages ng... walang mga advertisements, umaabot minsan ng mga 1,000 to 3,000. Sa isang bayan, madaling gumawa ng balita eh. Barangay balita, Municipal, walang naglalagay ng holdapan.

Interviewer: Aside from local budget po, do you have any source of budget in publishing your paper?

Interviewee: Wala. Pero merong sitwasyon, hindi dito nangyari, sa Mandaluyong, sa back page... nakiusap ilagay 'yung kumpanya nila. Sabi ko, "Ikaw gumastos no'n" kasi mahal, 45,000 copies, 'yun din 'yung number of households sa Mandaluyong noong nandoon pa ako.

Interviewer: Dito po sa Silang, what are the factors that the municipality considered in establishing the paper?

Interviewee: At my own initiative 'to eh. Walang inutos ang Mayor, hindi pa man ako empleyado, nag-issue ako ng 5,000 copies, nakatuwaan, sabi sa akin ituloy na. At 'yon, hindi 'yon every month, every two months or three months... tuwing kelan ko gusto lumabas. 'Pag ka marami akong trabaho o tinatamad, walang dyaryo. Kagaya noon nag-usap kami ni Mayor, eh 'yun namang mga staffs ko eh may lakad... kaya kinabukasan kami gumawa.

Interviewer: Ah so nakadepende po sa inyo. . .

Interviewee: Yes, at eto pa isang ugali ko. May lalapit, mga magagaling na writer, "Oh Lolo Totsi, gagawa ako column dyan, igawan mo ko ng isang column dyan," deretso ako magsalita, hindi pwede. Ako nagpakahirap dito, gumawa ka ng sarili mong dyaryo. Pranka ako magsalita, kaya lahat ng nakasulat 'don, lahat galing sakin, ako nag-gather.

Interviewer: What difficulties were encountered in establishing the paper?

Interviewee: Walang problema, ang problema lang ay 'yung mga gustong mag-column at magbigay ng balita... which I do not accept. Halimbawa, may

magbibigay ng balita tapos titingnan ko, maganda ba... sige ako gagawa ng istorya. Hindi 'yung manunulat ang kausap ko, barangay captain, department head, kamukha nito, merong isang babaeng matanda, awardee ng ano. . . woman of the year, pinuntahan ko sa bahay, kinunan ko ng litrato. 'Nung lumabas ang dyaryo, binabasa ng mga anak, umiiyak ang mga anak. Ang balakid ko, kapag may mga lumalapit na gustong gumawa ng column. Lalapit sa Mayor, tatangi ang Mayor, kausapin mo si Lolo Totsi.

Interviewer: Ano ano po 'yung nag-motivate sa inyo. . . dito sa Silang?

Interviewee: Eh wala eh (dyaryo) so gumawa ako. Saka maganda 'yung nalalaman ng iba 'yung mga nangyayari kamukha nito, Silang, napakalawak nito, pangalawa sa pinakamalawak ito sa buong Cavite. Maragondon ang pinakamalawak. So, para makarating ang balita.

Pinakamahirap sa'kin eh circulation. Kasi 'pag binigay mo sa barangay captain ang isang daan, dalawampu laang ang maipamimigay. So, anong ginawa ko? Sa mga schools, inuuwi ng mga bata. Para naman maging interesado 'yung mga principals, supervisors, inilalagay ko sila sa balita. Halimbawa, ikaw principal, magsusulat ako ng balita tungkol sa'yo, hindi mo ipapakalat sa mga estudyante mo? Ang pinakamahirap circulation sa'kin. So, 'yun ang paraan ko. Ngayon, naglagay ako sa mga bangko, Jollibee, mini stop.

Interviewer: How did the newspaper get its name po?

Interviewee: Ang pangalan nung nakaraang Mayor. . . "Areng" Clarito L. Poblete. Naisipan ko, 'di ba may arangkada? Ginawa kong "Arengkada" Arengkadang Balita ng Silang... pwedeng arangkadang balita ng Silang, ano? Ginawa kong arengkada, tapos may litrato nya.

Interviewer: Hanggang ngayon po 'yun parin po... so, wala po kayong editorial staff, kayo lang po talaga gumawa lahat?

Interviewee: Oo, saka hindi ako naglalagay ng opinyon. 'Yun na mismong balita ang ino-opinyon ko, tinu-twist ko nang onti lang. Hindi ako naglalagay ng editorial, puro news. Pero tinu-twist nang konti, 'yung opinyon mo na gagawan ng balita.

Interviewer: Ah. . . feature news po. Babalikan lang po natin, may sarili po kayong printing press?

Interviewee: Wala, pinapagawa sa labas. Although bumili ako ng isang segunda-mano, hindi ko naman nagagamit. . .

Interviewer: Sa tanong po na paano nasi-circulate, through school po.

Interviewee: Kasi karanasan ko, 'pag nagbigay ako sa barangay captain ng isang daan (100), after one week makikita mo nakatambak parin do'n eh. Ang ginagawa ko, sa school, kada limandaan estudyante, binibigyan ko, edi may 500 na kagad.

Kung magtatayo kayo... ganito gawin nyo, kausapin nyo Mayor, una tiisin nyo, ma-hone mahasa ang inyong utak. Hindi lamang sa pagsusulat, pati sa paggawa ng dyaryo. 'Yun ang ultimate goal nyo, hindi nyo pa motive na bumira, gumawa ng balita, kundi ma-practice ang mga nalalaman ninyo. So, wala muna 'yung mga negative thoughts. . . magamit 'yung kaalaman ninyo. So, susunod kayo sa tenets nung kakausapin ninyong tao. Puro magagandang balita about the community, hindi mo kailangang purihin nang purihin ang Mayor eh. Sasabihin mo lang 'yung ginawa nya. Hindi mo sasabihin na magaling si Mayor, sasabihin mo lamang 'yung ginagawa nila. Ngayon, papaya at papayag 'yon.

Magsimula kayo 1,000 copies lamang, 4 pages, maghanap kayo ng imprenta kung meron don. Kung ano 'yung size ng makina 'yun yung size ng bibilhin ninyong papel. 'Wag na 'yung gusto mong size ang lalabas, naku hindi... kung ano'ng size ng makina, yun ang source ang dyaryo ko. Para walang tapon ang papel. Hindi ako gumagawa ng dyaryo sa gusto kong size, inaalang ko size ng makina at 'yun ang pabibili kong papel. Kasi 'pag sa size mo gusto at may papel kang sobra, babayaran mo 'yung tapon na 'yon eh.

"Magsimula kayo ng 1,000 copies, baka meron dung well printing press, gagastos muna o kaya tindahan, back page... full page advertisement, sya gagasta. 'yun ang hanapin niyo. Halimbawa sa Indang... aanuwin nyo, ano'ng kompanya nando'n, anong tindahan sikat do'n? O kaya Mayor mismo, i-offer nyo sarili nyo, magtrabaho kayo, sabihin nyo "Libre ho kami." 'Pag 1,000 copies siguro gagastos ka ng P1,500.00.

Date of Interview:

Interviewee: Mr. Jayvee Atas Masigla

Name of Printed Publication: MDS Newsletter

Position: Administrative Aide (Tourism Office)

Interviewer: Meron po bang estimated budget kayo noon 'pag nagpapa-publish po kayo ng dyaryo?

Interviewee: Wala syang ano... budget, kasi... hmm kasi ang ano lang namin ay bond paper, 'yung mga tape na ginagamit namin. Lahat sa budget na ng tourism.

Interviewer: So, bali... 'yun, 'dun lang din po talaga kumukuha sa local budget po?

Interviewee: Sa budget ng... sa budget namin ng tourism department.

Interviewer: Ano po 'yung mga factors na kinonsider ninyo sa pag-e establish ng newspaper aside po sa budget?

Interviewee: So... gusto lang namin... gusto lang ng boss ko na magkaroon ng newspaper every month ang Trece Martirez since 2013. Bukod 'don sa newspaper, meron kaming blog... blogspot. So, kung ano 'yung nakalagay na articles sa newsletter namin nasa blogspot din namin... lgu.trecemartirezcity@blogspot

Interviewer: Pero ano po... bukod 'don, nakitaan nyo rin po ba na kailangan din talaga sa Trece ng dyaryo?

Interviewee: Kailangan sya... kasi para makita ng buong Trece kung anong ginagawa at project ng Mayor.

Interviewer: Sa pag-e-establish po ng dyaryo, ano po 'yung mga difficulties na na-encounter nyo po?

Interviewee: Ang hirap mag-collect ng data... sa pagkuha ng mga data nang every month... ng ginagawa ng city... ng bawat department. Katulad nung sa health, sa DSWD, 'yung mga ginagawa nila. 'Yung fire, 'yung fire prevention month, 'yung March... 'nung March. Tapos nade-delay din sila sa pagbibigay ng data.

Interviewer: Hindi po kayo nagbibigay ng parang deadline?

Interviewee: ...Sinasabi namin pero... hindi din naman nila inaano eh.

Interviewer: 'Yung mga ano po... kumukuha po ng data, sino-sino po 'yon? Kayo-kayo rin po... o meron po kayong mga tao... designated?

Interviewee: Ako lang... kasi tatlo lang kami sa tourism, so, 'yung boss ko na si Miss Cherlene, tapos 'yung isa naman about naman sa administrative... about sa mga offices, ako naman about sa mga information.

Interviewer: So ano po 'yung parang nag-motivate... motivation other than sa sinabi nyo po na bakit po kayo nakapag-establish ng dyaryo? Bukod po sa kailangan talaga ng Trece, may mga idadagdag pa po ba kayo na naging motivation po para makapag-establish po ng dyaryo?

Interviewee: 'Yun lang eh... kasi para lang malaman ng mga taga-Treceño na ano... na 'yun 'yung ginagawa namin ni Mayor Melan.

Interviewer: So, sa pangalan po ng dyaryo, pa'no po nakuha 'yon o pa'no po na-come up?

Interviewee: 'Yung MDS? Moving Directly to Success 'to eh, bago 'tong MDS na 'to, nagkaroon muna kami ng parang isip kung anong magandang word din don sa name ni Mayor na Melan... Melandrez De Sagun. Maraming nag-isip

na mga head about dun sa... mga suggestion pero ito 'yung napili, 'yung Moving Directly to Success.

Interviewer: So, 'yung mga nagde-decide ng pangalan po, kayo kayo lang din po or meron po talagang specific na group?

Interviewee: ...tourism council. 'Yun lang.

Interviewer: Sa Editorial Staffs po meron po kayong...

Interviewee: Ito. (*pointed at the calendar on the wall wherein pictures and designations are being printed*)

Interviewer: Pa'no po pinipili? May mga qualifications po ba kayong nilagay para masabi po na, "Sige, dito ka sa... writer ka... parang ganun po.

Interviewee: Hindi eh, kasi dito sa... katulad nito (showing the newsletter) si Mayor Melan ang chairman tapos ang publisher si Mayora Aiza, pero tinanggal na namin si Mayora Aiza kasi nag-resign na sya... dito sa city, hindi pwede naman ilagay dito sa newsletter ang hindi employado ng Government.

Interviewer: So, para pong 'yung mga naging editorial staffs po 'yung parang mga naging heads po ng bawat ano po...

Interviewee: Hindi, ang nilagay lang namin sa parang... kami talaga sa tourism, kaming tatlo lang 'yun sa editorial, parang contribution 'yung mga staffs ng Mayor's office... 'yung mga matataas sa Mayor's office. Katulad nung admin, 'yung senior executive assistant, 'yung EA saka 'yung EA1 and 2.

Interviewer: Sa production naman po ninyo noon, meron po ba kayong sariling printing press o 'yung printer lang po talaga.

Interviewee: 'Yan lang talaga.. ni-request talaga namin 'yan para sa newsletter.

Interviewer: So kasama na po 'yan sa budget para po sa una po?

Interviewee: Oo, oo... Katulad nito may dumating pang isang ganyan (pointed at the printer) para du'n sa newsletter. Kasi ang target namin noon every year nataas 'yung newsletter. Halimbawa, 200 this, next year 300...

Interviewer: Paano po nasi-circulate 'yung paper, pa'no po nakakarating sa ibang tao 'yung newspaper nyo po?

Interviewee: Sa department na kami namigay noon eh, tapos nilalagay nalang namin 'to sa main information (desk) dyan, tapos 'yung iba dina-direct dito kapag kailangan ng mga students.

Interviewer: So, parang wala pong malalapit sa barangay na pwede pong kunin nila, pupunta pa po talaga dito parang ganun po?

Interviewee: 'Yun sana maganda na dadalhin sa barangay pero wala kasing magdadala, kulang kami ng staff.

Interviewer: Gaano po kadalas 'yung pagre-release po ninyo noon ng paper?

Interviewee: Every month.

Interviewer: Wala pong palya 'yon?

Interviewee: Wala pa...

Interviewer: Since 2013 pa po?

Interviewee: Simula noong 2013 na newsletter, simula nung naging top sya sa school.

Interviewer: Pero ito po 'yung ka-unahang newspaper?

Interviewee: Hm, pangatlo na 'to tapos every year din namin binabago 'yung layout.

APPENDIX E

Thematic Analysis

Thematic Analysis

General Problem: How is community media transforming within the digital environment?

QUESTION	INTERVIEW EXTRACT	CODE	THEME
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Part I. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

A. Media Ownership

If you could recall, who first managed your paper and how was it back then?

Participant 1: “ ‘Yun ‘yung Balitang Indang. Pero unfortunately, naka-stop na ‘yung publication niya as of now. So, wala kami. ‘Yun nga ‘yung first and last na lumabas ‘yun e. Parang nu’ng ni-release ‘yung publication na printed, the end of 2016, in-activate na rin ‘yung social media account tapos ‘yung website pinaayos ko na rin by 2017. ‘Yun ‘yung, alangan na, natambakan na na rin kami ng trabaho, alangan naman na ako ulit gumawa no’n lahat.”

Owned by LGU

Privately-owned (Individual Ownership)

Varied Ownership

Participant 1: “ ‘Yun ‘yung Balitang Indang. Pero unfortunately, naka-stop na ‘yung publication niya as of now. So, wala kami. ‘Yun nga ‘yung first and last na lumabas ‘yun e. Parang nu’ng ni-release ‘yung publication na printed, the end of 2016, in-activate na rin ‘yung social media account tapos ‘yung website pinaayos ko na rin by 2017. ‘Yun ‘yung, alangan na, natambakan na na rin kami ng trabaho, alangan naman na ako ulit gumawa no’n lahat.”

Participant 2: “Si Mr. Eli Tapanan ‘yung unang humawak nitong newsletter dito sa Imus. Nagsimula talaga kami sa

scratch... 'yung printed media namin. Inalam namin kung paano magiging effective saka pa'no mae-engage 'yung Imuseños sa pagbabasa ng news. Saka ano... kung pa'no ma-desseminate 'yung newsletters nang maayos.

Participant 3: "At my own initiative 'to eh. Walang inutos ang Mayor, hindi pa man ako empleyado, nag-issue ako ng 5,000 copies, nakatuwaan, sabi sa akin ituloy na. At 'yon, hindi 'yon every month, every two months or three months... tuwing kelan ko gusto lumabas. 'Pag ka marami akong trabaho o tinatamad, walang dyaryo. Kagaya noon nag-usap kami ni Mayor, eh 'yun namang mga staffs ko eh may lakad... kaya kinabukasan kami gumawa."

Participant 4: "So... gusto lang namin... gusto lang ng boss ko na magkaroon ng newspaper every month ang Trece Martinez since 2013.

Participant 5: "Si Mayor mismo, kase gusto nya may malaman o maging updated ang mga tao sa Carmona sa mga nakamit o nagawa ng munisipyo under her term. Ang nagko-contribute ay yung mga iba't-ibang departments ng munisipyo, 'yung naa-accomplish nila, pinapasa nila dito tapos kame na nag aayos... nag iintact. Dito na din nagle-lay out. The simplest explanation for this is annual accomplishment ng munisipyo na ginawang magazine type.

Participant 1: "...ang naging ano ro'n kasi do'n kaya hindi na rin

naming kinonsider... napunta lahat sa social media saka sa website. Parang nu'ng ni-release 'yung publication na printed, the end of 2016, in-activate na rin 'yung social media account tapos 'yung website pinaayos ko na rin by 2017.

Participant 2: " 'Pag government kasi dapat 'yung mga newsletter nila available any time sa may gusto. Tapos para ma-secure namin 'yung papel, we make sure na it is released only through the official sites and pages ng Imus... tapos dapat may proper branding and included din dapat 'yung names ng employees na involved sa paggawa."

Participant 3: " 'Nung araw, type talaga, tapos dadalhin mo sa printing. . . ngayon may computer na, may spell check pa. Maliban nalang kung Tagalog. Ang community paper should be Tagalog. Lalo na't Cavite. 'Wag kayong maglalagay ng Ingles, pwede mag-taglish... wala masyadong nagbabasa ng Ingles."

Participant 4: "Bukod 'don sa newspaper, meron kaming blog... blogspot. So, kung ano 'yung nakalagay na articles sa newsletter namin nasa blogspot din namin... lgu.trecemartirezcity@blogspot."

Participant 1: "No'n kasi, 'di ko matandaan kung magkano lumabas per page... parang 11 pesos per page. Kasi ano sya, 'yung paper nya hindi 'yung

Varying amount

Lesser financial allocation

B. Budget Allocation

newspaper type. 'Yung glossy. Ang ginamit naming no'n is 'yung C2S na Wanted pa yata. Basta 'yung pang-page ng magazine."

How much did the local government allot for the production of your community newsletter when you were just starting?

Participant 3: "Ang costing nyan, depende sa number of copies. Habang dumadami, lumalaki presyo. Pero 'dun sa first thousand, 'pag sa imprenta ka pupunta, 'yung first one thousand bibigyan ka nila kagad ng rate. Ang gastos kagad 'yung running. Okay, ito talaga ang mga gastos, una 'yung pre-press, 'yung pagga-gather ng information, you'll use gasoline... mag-i-interview ka, mama-masahe ka. Pagkuha ng litrato, 'di kamukha nung araw, ngayon digital na. . . papa-print mo nalang. 'Yun ang initial costing, 'yun ang pre-press."

Participant 4: "Wala syang ano... budget, kasi... hmm kasi ang ano lang namin ay bond paper, 'yung mga tape na ginagamit namin. Lahat sa budget na ng tourism."

Participant 5: "Since nagre-release kame annually ang budget for 5,000 copies is 300,000.00."

Participant 1: "Accounting pa rin. Pero may budget kasi kami for PIO namin, 'yung Public Information Officer, under din ng Office of the Mayor. So, doon, meron kaming allotted budget para sa ganyan na kinukuhanan namin."

Participant 2: "Ah sa finances, lahat naman ng local government talagang tsini-check

nila saka nire-review yearly 'yung para sa disbursement the following year. Talagang strict saka meticulous 'yung pagba-budget. As one of the duties of the City Information Office, we must allot a budget for the City paper and produced monthly issues... regardless kung may maka-receive kami ng budget cut or not.”

Participant 3: “Una, ang style ko, hindi ako pumupunta sa imprenta, eto ang gagawin ko... jabber style, kunwari ako ang naghahanap buhay, printer lang sila. So, ako, ang dadalhin ko sa kanila... camera ready. Nagawa na nung mga staffs ko 'yung istorya, andun na litrato naka-USB, ibabato nila sa plate maker sa Maynila. Pagdala nila sa Maynila, 350 per plate lamang, 4 pages. Pag ka nag-eight pages, 700. Ngayon, etong gimmick, 'yung transportation... edi ibabato nila by internet, pero 'yung plato o plantsa ipapadala dito, babayaran ko ng 250 'yon. Isasakay sa bus, ibaba roon sa imprenta. Two fifty plus two fifty... ngayon may running, sa first 1,000 no'n 350, succeeding 1,000, 250 nalang.”

Participant 4: “Sa budget ng... sa budget namin ng tourism department.”

Participant 5: “Wala. Local budget lang talaga ng munisipyo.”

Participant 1: “No'n kasi, 'di ko matandaan kung magkano

lumabas per page... parang 11 pesos per page. Kasi ano sya, 'yung paper nya hindi 'yung newspaper type. 'Yung glossy. Ang ginamit naming no'n is 'yung C2S na Wanted pa yata. Basta 'yung pang-page ng magazine."

Participant 3: "Ang costing nyan, depende sa number of copies."

How do you manage your finances back then?

Participant 1: "Accounting pa rin. Pero may budget kasi kami for PIO namin, 'yung Public Information Officer, under din ng Office of the Mayor. So, doon, meron kaming allotted budget para sa ganyan na kinukuhanan namin."

Funded by the LGU

Individual Strategy

Dependence to LGU

Financial Independence

Participant 2: "Ah sa finances, lahat naman ng local government talagang tsini-check nila saka nire-review yearly 'yung para sa disbursement the following year. Talagang strict saka meticulous 'yung pagba-budget. As one of the duties of the City Information Office, we must allot a budget for the City paper and produced monthly issues... regardless kung may maka-receive kami ng budget cut or not."

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Maynila, 350 per plate lamang, 4 pages. Pag ka nag-eight pages, 700. Ngayon, etong gimmick, 'yung transportation... edi ibabato nila by internet, pero 'yung plato o plantsa ipapadala dito, babayaran ko ng 250 'yon. Isasakay sa bus, ibaba roon sa imprenta. Two fifty plus two fifty... ngayon may running, sa first 1,000 no'n 350, succeeding 1,000, 250 nalang."

Participant 4: "Sa budget ng... sa budget namin ng **tourism department.**"

Participant 5: "Wala. **Local budget lang talaga ng munisipyo.**"

Social Media as a Platform is Free

Cheaper Expenses

What are your observed differences in terms of finances now that you are using internet and electronics compared when you are printing hard copies?

Participant 1: "...itong **sa social media, wala rin naman tayo... kumbaga free naman siya.** 'Yung website, 'yung official website kasi **binabayaran namin 'yung domain, 'yung hosting.** So, ayun 'yung mga technical aspect na kailangan mong bayaran. Nababayaran naman namin sya. Subscription kumbaga. Kasi kailangan mo 'yung domain no'n na binibili mo, 'yung www.lndang.ph."

Website's Domain is paid

Digitized version made the budget preparation easier

Participant 2: "Sa ngayon... du'n sa **digitized version ng newsletter namin, it made it easier to comply with the required papers for budget preparation.** Kaso, we are still producing the same number of printed copies as before, considering the budget

Budget is not a problem

Undisrupted Budget

How is the management of budget at present considering the pandemic and inflation?

allocation that we receive annually. We also usually have more copies during the first half of the year.”

Participant 1: “...walang cost kasi nga **na sa’yo na lahat e.**”

Participant 2: “Actually, ‘yung Administration and the Budget Office... they value effective and accurate information dissemination tapos tinitingnan din naman nila na essential ‘yung newsletter sa public. So, **the City Information Office still receives a considerable budget** to accomplish its deliverables for the people.”

C. Manpower

How do you describe the role designation or appointment when you first started your paper?

Participant 1: “ ‘yun nga ang naging challenge kaya hindi na siya na-revive, ‘yung printed version. Kasi do’n mo mari-realize na talagang kailangan mo ng isang entity sa ganitong institution na parang media. Meron ka rin talaga for PR saka na media dapat na team. Kasi ang nangyari no’n **kumuha lang ako per department ng contributors... ng mga empleyado.** So, from agriculture kukuha ka ng isa. Tapos from sa anong department, kung sino man na ano, kukuha ka lang. Tapos sila ‘yung pag-iisipin mo, e hindi naman talaga sila nakatutok do’n. Parang ano lang ‘yon e, parang side work nila. Ang focus pa rin nila ay ‘yung task talaga nila. **Actually, hindi nila nagagawa kasi hindi talaga sila para do’n. Unlike kapag meron kang team na media talaga, ‘yun lang, kumbaga naka-focus ka na mag-isip ng article.**”

There were assigned contributors

Unbalanced Workforce

One-man production

Participant 2: “ ‘Yung transitioning ko from Congress to the Local Government Unit and being appointed as the Acting City Information Officer was a pressure and a challenge, but, at the same time, a learning experience for me to grow as an individual while serving my City.”

Participant 3: “Halimbawa, may magbibigay ng balita tapos titingnan ko, maganda ba... sige ako gagawa ng istorya. Hindi ‘yung manunulat ang kausap ko, barangay captain, department head, kamukha nito, merong isang babaeng matanda, awardee ng ano... woman of the year, pinuntahan ko sa bahay, kinunan ko ng litrato. ‘Nung lumabas ang dyaryo, binabasa ng mga anak, umiiyak ang mga anak. Ang balakid ko, kapag may mga lumalapit na gustong gumawa ng column. Lalapit sa Mayor, tatanggi ang Mayor, kausapin mo si Lolo Totsi.”

Participant 4: “Ako lang... kasi tatlo lang kami sa tourism, so, ‘yung boss ko na si Miss Cherlene, tapos ‘yung isa naman about naman sa administrative... about sa mga offices, ako naman about sa mga information.”

Participant 5: “Sa mga departments kasi may isa sa kanilang tinatawag na “Liason Officer”. Sila ‘yung naka-assign magsulat ng accomplishment report ng department nila.”

How do you compare the number of staffs back then now that you transitioned to digital?

Participant 1: “ ‘Yung sa social media ang gumagawa lang ako... ako lang ang nag-a approve. Minsan ako na rin ang naggagawa ng write up. Tapos may isa akong staff na gano’n din, minsan papa-check nya sa’kin, sya ‘yung gagawa ng write up... mabilis.”

Less manpower was observed

Observed Decrease in Manpower in the Past

What are the selection processes to become a part of the paper back then?

Participant 1: “Usually, du’n sa department na concern. ‘Pag culture, ang ano niyan... tourism. Tapos depende kung meron kaming resource person coming from another department. Halimbawa meron dito do’n sa assessor, nu’ng nabubuhay pa ‘yung dating boss naming, si Sir Chito... so, marami syang connection, marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling ‘yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.”

Writers must have knowledge or concern with the topic

Varied Selection Process in the Past

Writers can be referred

Participant 2: “It is the decision of the City Information Officer and the head writer to choose the people who will be part of the paper. Usually, they select newsletter staff within the City Information Office or hire additional employees.”

Participant 4: “...ang nilagay lang namin sa parang... kami talaga sa tourism, kaming tatlo lang ‘yun sa editorial, parang contribution ‘yung mga staffs ng Mayor’s office... ‘yung mga matataas sa Mayor’s office. Katulad nung admin, ‘yung senior executive assistant, ‘yung EA saka ‘yung EA1 and 2.

Is there any difference in terms of role selection in the past when compared to the present. If yes, could you please explain.

Participant 1: “ ‘yun nga ang naging challenge kaya hindi na siya na-revive, ‘yung printed version. Kasi do’n mo mari-realize na talagang kailangan mo ng isang entity sa ganitong institution na parang media. Meron ka rin talaga for PR saka na media dapat na team. Kasi ang nangyari no’n kumuha lang ako per department ng contributors... ng mga empleyado. So, from agriculture kukuha ka ng isa. Tapos from sa anong department, kung sino man na ano, kukuha ka lang. Tapos sila ‘yung pag-iisipin mo, e hindi naman talaga sila nakatutok do’n. Parang ano lang ‘yon e, parang side work nila. Ang focus pa rin nila ay ‘yung task talaga nila. Actually, hindi nila nagagawa kasi hindi talaga sila para do’n. Unlike kapag meron kang team na media talaga, ‘yun lang, kumbaga naka-focus ka na mag-isip ng article.

Obvious difference due to wide selection of topics

Apparent Change in the Designation of Tasks

Participant 2: “ ‘Yung transitioning ko from Congress to the Local Government Unit and being appointed as the Acting City Information Officer was a pressure and a challenge, but, at the same time, a learning experience for me to grow as an individual while serving my City.”

Participant 3: “Halimbawa, may magbibigay ng balita tapos titingnan ko, maganda ba... sige ako gagawa ng istorya. Hindi ‘yung manunulat ang kausap ko, barangay captain, department head, kamukha nito, merong isang babaeng matanda,

awardee ng ano... woman of the year, pinuntahan ko sa bahay, kinunan ko ng litrato. 'Nung lumabas ang dyaryo, binabasa ng mga anak, umiiyak ang mga anak. Ang balakid ko, kapag may mga lumalapit na gustong gumawa ng column. Lalapit sa Mayor, tatanggi ang Mayor, kausapin mo si Lolo Totsi."

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marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling ‘yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.”

Participant 2: “It is the decision of the City Information Officer and the head writer to choose the people who will be part of the paper. Usually, they select newsletter staff within the City Information Office or hire additional employees.”

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Participant 1: “Oo, meron pa rin kaming gano’n. Usually gano’n ‘yung tina-tap namin. Actually, ngayon mas lumaki kasi minsan meron kaming mga articles or kagaya ng Bonifacio Day... ‘yung celebration ng Bonifacio Day. Meron kaming sarili pero minsan kumukuha kami ng info from National Government—Philippine Information Agency.”

Part 2: “Syempre oo. There is a more apparent designation of tasks based on the employees’ capabilities, experience, and qualifications compared nu’ng nagsisimula pa lang kami...”

Part II. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:

Production Process

A. Content Gathering

Before the pandemic, how did it feel to plan for news and information gathering?

Participant 1: “Noon kasi, usually, may regular meeting kami noon. **Madali.** Kumbaga andu’n na ‘yung pinakaano mo, du’n ka lang mag-iisip kung ano’ng ipapasok mong articles.”

News planning is much easier in the past

Easier News and Information Planning

Participant 2: “**Nagpapatawag** ako ng meeting tapos parang ginawan ko sya ng **organizational chart.** Kumbaga **direction, naka-flow chart ‘yung articles,** ‘yung pinaka-structure ng newsletter. So, meron kaming main feature, ito ‘yung tungkol sa mandate ni Mayor, ‘yung ginagawa nya tapos meron kang mga articles do’n na naka-focus sa history, sa environment, sa tourism, culture... so, nakagano’n lang sya.”

How do you designate the beat or piece of information back when

Participant 3: “**‘Nung araw, type talaga, tapos dadalhin mo sa printing.** . . . ngayon may computer na, may spell check pa. Maliban nalang kung Tagalog. Ang community paper should be Tagalog. Lalo na’t Cavite. ‘Wag kayong maglalagay ng Ingles, pwede mag-taglish...

Designation of beat is much easier in the past

<i>there is no disruption in terms of physical movement?</i>	wala masyadong nagbabasa ng Ingles.”	Participant 1: “Usually, du’n sa department na concern.	Finding appropriate human source is a must	Easier Beat Designation
<i>How do you set up interviews before pandemic?</i>	‘Pag culture, ang ano niyan... tourism. Tapos depende kung meron kaming resource person coming from another department. Halimbawa meron dito do’n sa assessor, nu’ng nabubuhay pa ‘yung dating boss naming, si Sir Chito... so, marami syang connection, marami syang alam regarding sa culture ng Indang. So, sa kanya nanggagaling ‘yung... sya nag-aano. So, depende kung sino ang pinakaano... na resource person.”	Setting up interview including request must be conducted first		
<i>In relation, now that you are in a digital environment, how do you find your content gathering?</i>	Participation 1: “Meron kami, ‘yung pinaka-interview na kinconduct is during newsletter time. ‘Yung printed. Kasi do’n nga, ang nangyari sa kanya ay para syang magazine type e. Kagaya no’n, ‘yung pinakamatandang magkakalamay sa Indang ininterview. So, pati ‘yon naghanap sila ng mga resource person do’n na magbibigay ng story tungkol sa ano ng kalamay. ‘Yung mga gano’n, ‘yun ‘yung kaibahan sa social media.”	It is much easier to find content using social media	Ethical Gathering of Human Source	
<i>Is there any difference compared to the past? If there is, could you please explain.</i>	Participation 2: “We usually set up an interview by sending a request letter or a memo to the office or employees involved with the program or project.”	Traditional content gathering has planning and requires more preparation	Digital Environment Provides Adequate Amount of Content	
	Participant 1: “Sa Facebook naman, sa social media, mabilis kaya lang hindi sya...”	Nothing changed		

	<p>Participant 2: “As before, we connect with different offices... tapos ‘yung mga researchers namin, they verify muna the contents they gathered before giving the details to the writer saka pa nila ipo-post or print for public consumption.”</p>		
	<p>Participant 1: “...sa newsletter mas pinag-iisipan mo. Meron talagang planning. Unlike social media, para syang ‘yung news talaga na on-the-go ka e kung ano’ng nangyayari. Kailangan sumabay ka. So, magkaiba sila ng discipline kumbaga. So, ‘yun ‘yung ano natin do’n.”</p>	<p>Traditional manner of content gathering is more expensive</p>	<p>Traditional Content Gathering is Meticulously Managed</p>
	<p>Participant 2: “None. Wala naman. The functions of the City Information Office remain the same as before. Nagdo-document pa rin kami saka cover... halos same pa rin kasi we are still gathering information, researching, editing, posting, and disseminating information on current events, programs, news, and announcements. Lahat ‘yon for the benefit of the public.</p>		
<p>B. Content Packaging</p> <p><i>Before the pandemic, how was your way of writing?</i></p>	<p>Participant 3: “Okay, ito talagang mga gastos, una ‘yung pre-press, ‘yung pagga-gather ng information, you’ll use gasoline... mag-i-interview ka, mama-masahe ka. Pagkuha ng litrato, ‘di kamukha nung araw, ngayon digital na. . . papa-print mo nalang. ‘Yun ang initial costing, ‘yun ang pre-press.”</p>	<p>Articles could be produced by contributors</p> <p>Way of writing</p>	<p>Purely developmental</p>

	<p>Participant 4: “Ang hirap mag-collect ng data... sa pagkuha ng mga data nang every month... ng ginagawa ng city... ng bawat department. Katulad nung sa health, sa DSWD, ‘yung mga ginagawa nila. ‘Yung fire, ‘yung fire prevention month, ‘yung March... ‘nung March. Tapos nade-delay din sila sa pagbibigay ng data.</p>	<p>remains the same</p> <p>Sunshine journalism was evident</p>	
<p><i>How about editing and lay-outing?</i></p>	<p>Participant 1: “Ang pagsusulat nu’ng time ng newsletter... ng printed nga... ah ano sya, kumbaga manggagaling ang mga articles sa mga tao. Sa mga tao, ‘yung mga nagsusulat talaga. Tapos ‘yon babasahin mo. Then, afterwards re-review-hin mo pa, ipu-proofread mo pa... ‘yung mga gano’n.”</p>	<p>One-man production</p>	<p>Unequal distribution of editing and lay-outing task</p>
<p><i>Is it easier now that you are in a digital environment? If yes, how do say so?</i></p>	<p>Participant 2: “There’s no particular difference in news writing pre and post-pandemic.”</p> <p>Participant 3: “...‘Pag ka community paper, puro magaganda, pagka ‘yung Tabloid style naman, may investigative reporting, pero pag ka community newspaper... puro magagandang balita ng komunidad. ‘Di kamukha ng mga newspaper dito sa Cavite, merong mga binibira. ‘Yung dyaryo ko dito eh... community newspaper na walang pangit na balita. Kasi aral ako kay Marcos... ‘yung developmental information. Before Martial Law reporter na ako ng The Manila Times, ‘nung mag-martial law,</p>	<p>Unchanged editing and lay-outing procedure</p> <p>Easier access</p>	

syempre susunod ka, puro magandang balita lang.”

What do you think are the challenges now that you are in a digital environment?

Participant 1: “...ako na rin. Kasi nga ‘yun ‘yung trabaho ko e. Nag-art director ako... creative director ako ng agency... creative agency. Mostly talaga, sa design talaga ang trabaho ko. Sa creative. ‘Yun ‘yung ginagamit ko. Kaya minsan talaga, kahit nu’ng time ng COVID, ‘yun na ‘yung... wala akong maasahan e. ‘Yan ‘yang mga ‘yan, ‘yang mga Indang Atin ‘To na mga yan... ako gumagawa nyan. Kasi nga wala ka ditong makukuhang tao. Na ‘yung sa discipline mo or galing sa industry mo na meron dito. Mahirap. Bihira. So, talagang tyatyagain mo sya. ‘Yun ‘yung challenge ng pagdya-dyaryo.”

Observed lack of creativity

Visual appeal and Content Presentation

Participant 2: “The writing, editing, and layout of the newsletter remain the same since we have staff naman na assigned to carry out their roles.”

Unsatisfied readers

Participant 2: “It is easier in terms of communication, the processing of online requests, contacting the requesting party, and fact-checking details for accurate information dissemination.”

<p>Part III. The Changing Nature of Community Media in a Digital Environment in terms of:</p> <p>Distribution Process</p> <p>A. Medium or Outlet</p> <p><i>How do you describe your medium or outlet back then?</i></p>	<p>Participant 1: “Kumbaga ano, hindi sila... ‘yun nga number one hindi gano’n ka-sharpen ‘yung creativity. So, kumbaga parang sila, kung ano lang ‘yung info, as is. Pero hindi nila ire-relay na parang storytelling.”</p> <p>Participant 2: “Sa challenge, siguro kapag hindi satisfied ‘yung readers namin tapos mga taga-Imus pa talaga sila. Since, our task is to deliver information to the public katulad ng programs, projects, and updates sa local government ng Imus, ginagawa talaga namin ‘yung best namin para ma-fact-check saka ma-verify bawat details na nari-receive namin.”</p> <p>Participant 2: “We have produced print and digital copies of the newsletter before the pandemic. Hanggang ngayon kasi meron pa rin kami.”</p> <p>Participant 1: “...‘yung paper nya hindi ‘yung newspaper type. ‘Yung glossy. Ang ginamit naming no’n is ‘yung C2S na Wanted pa yata. Basta ‘yung pang-page ng magazine. ...‘yung glossy na coated tapos back-to-back ‘yon pero isang page lang sya na malaki e na size ng newspaper pero kapag hinawakan mo sya glossy sya.”</p> <p>Participant 3: “ ‘Yung dyaryo ko dito eh... community newspaper na walang pangit na balita. Kasi aral ako kay Marcos... ‘yung developmental information.”</p>	<p>There are two existing platforms for their media (printed newsletter and digital) A more luxurious output due to paper type which is glossy or magazine type</p> <p>Expensive looking</p>
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<p><i>What is a more convenient outlet for you? Please explain.</i></p>	<p>Participant 2: "Of course, digital is more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce e. However, we still encourage the public to read the paper through the physical document given to them; thus, we display these in every office as much as possible."</p>	<p>Digital releases are more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce</p>	<p>Digital outlet is more convenient</p>	
<p><i>What is the challenge of transforming your medium and realigning it with the demands of a digital environment? Please explain.</i></p>	<p>Participant 1: "...itong sa social media, wala rin naman tayo... kumbaga free naman siya."</p>	<p>Participant 2: "One of the challenges we sometimes face is that social media users tend not to read the whole caption or context of the post, resulting in misconception and misunderstanding that could potentially cause the further proliferation of fake news. Another challenge siguro... na we usually encounter is photo grabbers using the published materials of the City without giving proper credit.</p>	<p>Digital releases are more convenient because physical copies require an additional workforce</p>	<p>Misinformation, Photo stealing, and Underemployment</p>
	<p>Participant 1: " 'Yun nga medyo mababa 'yung creativity na hindi mo naman pwede paghanapan sila kasi sasabihin nila, "Hindi naman namin trabaho 'yan." So, 'yun 'yung mga aspect na 'pag galing ka sa ano tapos gusto mong magkaro'n ng... mag-materialize 'yung concept na ginagamit mo sa ibang industry na ilalagay mo rito, so, pipigain mo talaga sila. Mahihirapan ka. So, maraming trabaho on your</p>			

	<p>part. Kumbaga sa'kin o kung dalawa lang kaming nakakaintindi halos kami lahat 'yung umaayos. So, kumbaga 'yung makukuha mo lang sa kanila ay piling pili lang.</p> <p>...Madami rin kasi... minsan 'yung pagko-construct mo ng paragraphs. Minsan paulit-ulit e. Kasi nasasanay kana nga. Minsan 'yung pinagawa ko, 'yung staff. Kina-copy paste nya from last year e. 'Yung info. Sabi ko kasi para mabilis gano'n tapos ine-edit ko na lang."</p>	<p>Unfit for job description</p>
<p>B. Frequency of Releasing</p> <p><i>How was the experience when you were still releasing your paper before the pandemic?</i></p>	<p>Participant 2: "Releasing and disseminating the printed newsletter monthly in every office... outside and or extension offices... and public schools... fulfilling sya actually because we could physically see the fruit of our hard work."</p> <p>Participant 3: "Una, ang style ko, hindi ako pumupunta sa imprenta, eto ang gagawin ko... jabber style, kunwari ako ang naghahanap buhay, printer lang sila. So, ako, ang dadalhin ko sa kanila... camera ready. Nagawa na nung mga staffs ko 'yung istorya, andun na litrato naka-USB, ibabato nila sa plate maker sa Maynila."</p> <p>Participant 1: " 'Yung sa release naman no'n since 'yun lang naman ang talaga ang advantage ng nasa local government ka or nasa government entity ka, 'yung</p>	<p>It is a fulfilling experience for them to see the actual fruit of their hard work</p> <p>Tedious yet fulfilling</p> <p>It is considered as an opportunity to manage the paper solely</p>

manpower mo saka ‘yung resources mo ay hindi sya magiging... unlike sa private... once na nag-publish ka or nag-release ka... merong cost. Syempre mag-aano ka pa rin naman... kung paano ka mag-release, kung paano mo sya ideploy kumbaga ‘yung materials mo. Ito, hinde, isang patawag mo lang ng meeting, patawag mo ‘yung mga Kapitan, bigyan mo ng tag-isang kopya tapos... kasi regular naman meeting namin e. So, anytime... kaya nga dito ‘yun ‘yung kagandahan e. Lahat ng resources mo, anytime, isang tawag mo lang wala kang problema.”

Participant 4: “Sa department na kami namigay noon eh, tapos nilalagay nalang namin ‘to sa main information (desk) dyan, tapos ‘yung iba dina-direct dito kapag kailangan ng mga students.”

Participant 5: “Namimigay kame sa mga barangays at schools, syempre for free ‘yun.”

Participant 1: “ ‘Yung pag-produce mo lang talaga coming from your side lalo na kung pa’no mo gagawin ‘yung materials. ‘Yun ‘yung challenge pero ‘yung pag-dispose mo, pag-disseminate mo physically ng mga materials napakadali. Napakadali. Wala kang problema. Wala pating cost. ‘Yun

Resources as well as releasing are not a problem

Releasing is never a challenge

How do you describe the challenges of releasing an issue back then?

na 'yung isa... walang cost kasi nga na sa'yo na lahat e."

Participant 4: "Ang hirap mag-collect ng data... sa pagkuha ng mga data nang every month... ng ginagawa ng city... ng bawat department."

Participant 3: "Walang problema, ang problema lang ay 'yung mga gustong mag-column at magbigay ng balita... which I do not accept. Halimbawa, may magbibigay ng balita tapos titingnan ko, maganda ba... sige ako gagawa ng istorya. Hindi 'yung manunulat ang kausap ko, barangay captain, department head, kamukha nito, merong isang babaeng matanda, awardee ng ano... woman of the year, pinuntahan ko sa bahay, kinunan ko ng litrato. 'Nung lumabas ang dyaryo, binabasa ng mga anak, umiiyak ang mga anak. Ang balakid ko, kapag may mga lumalapit na gustong gumawa ng column."

...Pinakamahirap sa'kin eh circulation. Kasi 'pag binigay mo sa barangay captain ang isang daan, dalawampu laang ang maipamimigay. So, anong ginawa ko? Sa mga schools, inuuwi ng mga bata. Para naman maging interesado 'yung mga principals, supervisors, inilalagay ko sila sa balita. Halimbawa, ikaw principal, magsusulat ako ng balita tungkol sa'yo, hindi mo ipapakalat sa mga estudyante mo? Ang pinakamahirap circulation sa'kin."

How you package your materials is more difficult than releasing an issue

There were questionable initiatives

It is much better now that they have shifted digitally

Now that you have shifted digitally, what have you observed when disseminating information to your community?

Participant 2: “One of the challenges of releasing an issue back then was the delay in printing. Also, events dated during the last week of the month would require some time for writers, editors, and proofreaders to produce articulated articles. May times na nae-experience pa rin namin pero mas better na ngayon kasi digital media na.”

There is minimal delay now

Information can be quickly disseminated in the digital environment

Easier Information Dissemination

Participant 5: “ ‘Yung laging problema is, minsan hindi nabibigay agad ‘yung report ng bawat departments kaya nade-delay ang printing.”

What are the advantages of releasing an issue in a digital environment?

Participant 2: “Information spreads in a blink, and sometimes people quickly comment without understanding the full context. ‘Yun ‘yung mahirap sa part ng digital.”

Social media offers a fast venue and serves as a reliable platform for their information dissemination initiatives

Faster News and Information Dissemination

Participant 1: “Social media madali. Ayun ‘yung napansin ko when it comes to... ‘yung mga government institution lalo na ‘yung may kailangan... usually kasi ikaw na hinahanap e. May kailangan sa’yo ang tao e. ‘Yung information coming from you sobrang importante. Kaya nga du’n pumapasok ‘yung ethics saka responsibility sobrang bigat din when it comes to institutions like this. Hindi kagaya sya ng private na... halimbawa meron kang blog or social media page na private... kailangan mong

Social media offers same routine unlike

mag-attract ng viewers, ng followers. Ikaw kukuha ng audience. Unlike itong sa amin kami ang inaantay ng tao na maglabas kasi automatic ‘yan meron e...”

in printed newsletter wherein the publication needs to conduct planning

Participant 2: “...Information dissemination has become easier and more accessible, especially for those who have constant access to the Internet.”

How about disadvantages at present?

Participant 2: “Not every Imuseño has the capability and time to check the official outlets of the City.”

Unfamiliarity with the official social media page

Smaller opportunity, digital divide, and lack of skills (in terms of Digital Media)

Participant 1: “ ‘Yon nga... number one is ito ‘yung institution mo, hindi naman sya... hindi sila exposed du’n sa media unlike ako... galing ako sa advertising, sa media talaga. Sa private. Dito, ang hirap mong iano... although alam nila na dapat may gano’n... merong pailan-ilan na tao na dapat alam nila na sa publication, meron kang... pero hindi lahat well-versed pagdating sa gano’n. Para kang nagsisimula sa scratch e. Tuturuan mo pa sila.”

Members of the publication has to undergo training due to lack of skills in digital media